

MATILDE

Migration Impact Assessment to Enhance
Integration and Local Development in
European Rural and Mountain Regions

COMPARATIVE REPORT ON SOCIAL INNOVATION PRACTICES

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MATILDE has received
funding from the European
Union's Horizon 2020
research and innovation
programme under grant
agreement No 870831

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Comparative Report on Social Innovation Practices

Call: H2020-SC6-MIGRATION-2019

Work Programmes:

H2020-EU.3.6.1.1. The mechanisms to promote smart, sustainable and inclusive growth

H2020-EU.3.6.1.2. Trusted organisations, practices, services and policies that are necessary to build resilient, inclusive, participatory, open and creative societies in Europe, in particular taking into account migration, integration and demographic change

Deliverable 3.4 Comparative report and social innovation practices

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Version: 30.06.2021

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5017793

This document was produced under the terms and conditions of Grant Agreement No. 870831 for the European Commission. It does not necessarily reflect the view of the European Union and in no way anticipates the Commission's future policy in this area.

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Introduction and summary of the research efforts

The Matilde Work Package 3 (WP 3) “Social impact assessment of migration”, led by UEF, conducted a multi-scale assessment of the social impacts of migration at the national and regional levels using the MATILDE toolbox and Matilde matrix developed earlier in the project within WP 2. The main task of the WP 3 was to measure and compare the impact of Third Country Nationals (TCNs), on different social structures and processes, measured through indicators that are understood as the dependent variables, in different MATILDE regions. A particular attention has been paid on the MATILDE social dimensions: social polarization and cohesion (as measured by social mobility, inclusion, and social capital, and with specific attention to xenophobic attitudes/anti-immigrant events, solidarity initiative/mobilization of organizations on topics related to TCNs), participation/active citizenship, service provision and social inclusion). Spatial aspects, with a focus on rural and mountain regions and urban-rural nexus, has been highlighted throughout all the research activities in the WP.

The WP has consisted of three tasks which were contributed to by all Matilde Research Partners. The fourth and last task has been run by UEF, and it has aimed at developing an integrated report elaborating the main findings of this WP. The aim of this task has been to compare data across national and regional contexts in order to better understand how TCNs impact varies across countries and regions and how it influences the social dimension of the receiving society. The social assessment conducted by the Consortium within the WP 3 began with a policy and governance analysis, which was then furthered by in-depth investigation relying on both quantitative and qualitative methods. In terms of concrete output, each of the tasks has produced its own deliverable, the last one providing a comparative synthesis of the entire WP, building on the earlier deliverables. In all, the WP has produced the following deliverables during the 11 months that WP was in operation:

- D3.1 Country-based policy briefings on migration-related social policies
- D3.2 Statistical briefings on social impacts
- D3.3 Country reports on social impacts
- D3.4 Comparative analysis and social innovation practices

WP3 TIMELINE: 11 MONTHS

START: 1 AUGUST 2020

END: 30 JUNE 2021

Figure 1. WP 3 timeline and research tasks.

DEFINING “THIRD COUNTRY NATIONALS”

Third Country Nationals (TCNs) a multifaceted and heterogeneous group of individuals (including economic and family migrants, students and researchers, highly skilled migrants, asylum seekers, refugees and status holders and vulnerable groups: victims of trafficking, unaccompanied minors, and stateless persons). Different types of migrants can all be assumed to behave differently from an integration perspective and their social impact on the receiving community differ.

In line with MATILDE’s focus on rural and mountain areas, the project devotes specific attention to groups of migrants whose impact in such areas may be more significant. It thus centres on economic migrants, family migrants and forced migrants (including asylum seekers, refugees, and status holders).

The dimensions of gender, age, education, and professional experience are regarded as cross-cutting categories influencing the positioning and integration path of TCNs in the contexts where they settle down and are thus considered as intervening variables within the assessments conducted in MATILDE. Specific subgroups, such as minors and victims of trafficking, will be considered in some local cases studies. Specific national groups will be in focus for their relevance in the development of integration policies in Europe.

NOTE: *the original proposal links the definition directly with integration: “The project considers ‘Third Country Nationals’ (TCNs) as non-EU citizens who are the target of EU integration policies”. However, in this WP, it was actively reminded that impact and integration are two different topics, and that we cannot instinctively assume a direct causality to exist between them. Also migrants who are not targeted by EU integration policies or choose not to integrate for whatever reason have an impact – in cases even more so than those who do integrate.*

*European Commission: “Any person who is not a citizen of the European Union within the meaning of Art. 20(1) of TFEU and who is not a person enjoying the European Union **right to free movement**, as defined in Art. 2(5) of the [Regulation \(EU\) 2016/399 \(Schengen Borders Code\)](#).”*

Sources:

- [Art. 3\(1\) of Directive 2008/115/EC \(Return Directive\)](#)
- [Art. 2\(6\) of Regulation \(EU\) 2016/399 \(Schengen Borders Code\)](#)

The first task (3.1: Migration-related social policy analysis, M7 to M11) began with a desk research phase, during which information concerning the existing relevant policies were collected. As a second step, in-depth interviews with major stakeholders were conducted to fill in any gaps in knowledge and to gain further insight to the policy making processes in order to perform a policy content analysis. The analysis conducted considered both the vertical and horizontal distribution on competences according to multilevel governance approach, focused on both the directly migration related social policies targeting TCNs as well as other policies e.g. housing, transportation, regional development) that can have indirectly social outcomes. The relevance of the spatial dimension of the policies was also considered to detect references to territorial (im)balance, urban/rural connections and whether and how integration policies reflect spatial specificities of the regions. The analysis resulted in ten country-based policy briefings on migration-related social policies having an impact on migration (D3.1) compiled by the research partners for their own country. Given the strong ties between social and economic policies, the consortium decided to merge Tasks 3.1 and 4.1, to avoid overlaps in actual research work as well as its results. Hence, the deliverable submitted contains both the social and economic aspect in one report. Each report included also separate conclusions on social and economic aspect to be built upon in the upcoming tasks.

The WP then continued with two parallel tasks: Task 3.2 Quantitative assessment of the social impact of TCNs and Task 3.3 Qualitative assessment of the social impact of TCNs, both of which lasted from M7 to M15. The quantitative assessment applied the MATILDE matrix and toolbox to provide a quantitative assessment of the Matilde social dimensions. Based on statistical data from e.g. Eurostat, Zaragoza indicators, European labour Force Survey, OECD database on migrants in OECD regions, as well as national and regional data, regression analyses and spatial econometrics of the social impact were performed. While the task succeeded in its aims, challenges emerged in the data collection process with regards to the robustness of the collected data as well as its availability at the same geographical scale. The adaptation strategy used aimed at using the statistical data which displayed the highest possible degree of harmonisation and the lowest number of missing data for entities and years to improve comparability of the results and to generate a robust dataset. The result of the task was ten country-based statistical briefing on the quantitative assessment of TCNs (D3.2), compiled by UEF with the support of all research partners.

The Qualitative assessment (Task 3.3) part relied on in-depth qualitative interviews and focus groups with key stakeholders (identified by the Stakeholder Involvement Plan, D2.8) in measuring and explaining qualitative impacts of TCNs. The task considered the effects of TCNs arrival and

settlement, such as for example changes taking place in the social structure, the problems connected to social exclusion and economic inequalities. It studied the interactions between demographic trends, access, and redistribution of material assets (e.g., historical housing patterns and land use) and service provision (e.g., opportunity to maintain schools open, public transport active, and related services due to the presence of TCNs). In particular, the task focused on practices of social innovation stemming from the direct, indirect, and induced effects of TCNs arrival and settling in in destination contexts. Each research partner was expected to carry out at least ten in-depth interviews at national and regional level with policy makers, expert groups and stakeholders, public service providers and caregivers, practitioners and organizations working on migration (directly or indirectly) related fields. In addition, at least three focus groups per partner were organized, physically or remotely depending on the situation, at the regional level. Each partner delivered a country-based report on the qualitative assessment of TCNs (D3.3).

This comparative report (D3.4) pulls together the key findings of the WP3. Rather than a fully-fledged comparison, however, it rather aims to highlight specific features, outcomes, and impact at the different levels of analysing throughout the MATILDE regions in order to better understand how TCNs impact varies across countries and regions and how it influences the social dimensions of the receiving society. The report is compiled based on the national reports provided by all the MATILDE research partners in the earlier WP 3 tasks. The case specific findings summarized here derive from the work of the respective case study teams. The report commences by conceptualising social impact and discusses the ways to analyse it. Based on the Task 3.1, it then provides an overview of migration related policies and governance in the MATILDE countries and brings to fore good practices from different case studies. It then proceeds to reflect upon the findings of the quantitative analysis (D4.2) before discussing the findings of the qualitative analysis on the social impact (D4.3). A SWOT analysis is provided at the end to synthesise the main strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats stemming from the conducted empirical research throughout the MATILDE regions.

Social impact

Assessing social impact, which is understood here as the changes to the social structure (demographic trends, social polarisation or inclusion, civic participation, service provision etc.) and

transformation of the life-world* (impact on the symbolic dimension and the culturally transmitted and linguistically organised reservoir of meaning patterns, is much more than a step-by-step process for identification of outcomes and fulfilment of legal requirements. It can be a mechanism for promoting social sustainability as well as a tool for positive social change (Momtaz & Kabir 2018).

) Habermas (1981): The lifeworld is **the everyday world that we share with others. This includes all aspects of life barring organised or institution-driven ones. For example, it includes family life, culture and informal social interactions. In short: it is **the sphere within which we lead much of our social and personal life**. The lifeworld is **based on a tacit fund of shared meanings and understandings** that enable us to perform actions that we know others will comprehend.*

Our assessment of social impact build on Vanclay's (2003) elaboration on the topic in including the processes of analysing, monitoring, and managing the intended and unintended social consequences, both positive and negative, of planned interventions (policies, programs, plans, projects) as well as any social change processes invoked by those interventions. In our assessment we have paid a particular attention to the following realms (adapted from Vanclay 2003):

- **people's way of life:** that is, how they live, work, play and interact with one another on a day-to-day basis;
- their **culture:** shared beliefs, customs, values and language or dialect;
- their **community:** its cohesion, stability, character, services and facilities;
- their **political systems:** the extent to which people are able to participate in decisions that affect their lives, the level of democratisation that is taking place, and the resources provided for this purpose;
- their **environment:** the quality of the air and water people use; the availability and quality of the food they eat; the level of hazard or risk, dust and noise they are exposed to; the adequacy of sanitation, their physical safety, and their access to and control over resources;
- their **health and wellbeing:** health is a state of complete physical, mental, social and spiritual wellbeing and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity;
- their **personal and property rights:** particularly whether people are economically affected, or experience personal disadvantage which may include a violation of their civil liberties;
- their **fears and aspirations:** perceptions about their safety, their fears about the future of their community, and their aspirations for their future and the future of their children.

These dimensions allow us to target not just migrant integration, but also the broader social impact on the contextualized social realm and everyday life; i.e., how migration is changing the life of the people in specific territories? The results must, however, be compared to the aspirations, capabilities, and rights of the resident population. The less differences between the natives and the immigrants are the better the chances for (a successful) inclusion of newcomers. Our data collection and case studies has been structured around the following MATILDE Social Dimensions (MSDs, see also Laine & Rauhut 2020).

- **Social polarization** that may arise by income inequality across socio-economic groups or co-existence of different ethnic groups. Specific attention has also been paid to xenophobic attitudes/anti-immigrant events, solidarity initiatives/ mobilization of organizations on topics related to TCNs),
- **Social cohesion** and its constitutive elements: social mobility (ability of individuals to change their economic status), social inclusion (possibility of individuals to take part in society) and social capital (cooperation, social bonds and trust among people);
- **Active participation** and citizenship rights (civic and political participation by TCNs, acquisition of equal rights/responsibilities, bridges and links between TCNs and local citizens, social capital);
- **Access to and quality of services** (including, but limited to, development of new jobs in the social sectors related to TCNs reception and integration activities, gaps between TCNs and locals in access and fruition of social services, education, and trainings, share of NEETs (Not in Education, Employment, or Training), housing, and use of public transport).

A positive social impact of immigration is not the same as a successful integration. We cannot assume causality between these concepts. A positive social impact of immigration is more than just integration; it is about the well-functioning of a society. A positive social impact of immigration on the host society is when a plus-sum game is achieved, i.e. immigrants and the integration of immigrants adds extra value to the society and this extra value would not have been created without immigrants. A negative social impact of immigration on the host society is when the opposite occurs. A negative social impact of immigration can also occur when a zero-sum game occurs, i.e. immigrants

take resources from natives and vice versa. In both cases, society is worse off with immigrants and the integration of immigrants than without them.

Formal institutions (e.g. laws, regulations, public agencies, and organisations) facilitate settlement and integration of immigrants, and these institutions interact with the policy process in the host country (Penninx 2003). Laws and policies explicitly and implicitly categorise immigrants as “wanted” and “unwanted” immigrants, or as immigrants “in need of integration” and immigrants who are “already integrated” or “beyond integration”. Hence, an immigrant’s integration is not only shaped by explicit integration policies, but also the way policies explicitly and implicitly perceive, problematise and categorise them (Mügge & van der Haar 2016). Informal institutions among immigrants, e.g. religion and culture, can determine the success of integration, and immigrant groups may become either an accepted part of society on the same level as comparable native groups, or they may isolate themselves or remain unrecognised and excluded (Penninx 2003; Penninx & Garcés-Masareñas). Just as the attitudes among immigrants towards the host society (i.e. its informal institutions) influence how integrated they will be, the attitudes extended towards immigrants is also determined by informal institutions among the native population (Rauhut 2020).

Among migration-related social policies, which cover most social policy related areas, formal institutions dominate – e.g. laws, regulations, public agencies, and organisations, while informal institutions – i.e. culture, attitudes, norms, or values – are scarce. The neglect of informal institutions in migration-related social policies results in misunderstandings and cultural clashes, something which can be assumed to reduce the positive social impacts of immigration (Søholt et al. 2012; Trondstad 2015). Successful migration related social policies, thus, need to target all involved actors, i.e. both immigrants and natives, as well as formal institutions (laws, rules, rights) or informal institutions (values, norms, attitudes).

Loop-sided migration-related policies relating to formal institutions and immigrants may cause social polarisation with natives, if they perceive that immigrants enjoy privileges, they themselves are not granted. While immigrants and natives are two potential target groups for migration-related social policies, often these policies mostly target “immigrants” in general or focus on refugees in particular. “Immigrants”, however, are far from a homogeneous group, whereby general approaches tend to obscure more than they illuminate. In Matilde, our aim has been to move towards an evidence-based evaluation model and utilise our case studies as benchmarks of good practice.

Overview of policies and governance

In **Austria**, a host of policies imply profound effects on the opportunities for socio-structural and socio-cultural integration and their opportunities to be included in societal institutions of all kinds. In 2015/2016 with the sudden increase of asylum seekers migration, integration issues have dominated many political debates and led to a heightened awareness for the issue and, later, a general change of attitudes towards newcomers. This included enhanced considerations on opportunities for migrants in rural regions, discussions of local development action focusing on “integration” and community engagement extending towards newcomers, and reflection of the beneficial effects in cultural and economic terms of increasing levels of migrants in small remote municipalities, including mountain valleys. Albeit the general feeling towards asylum seekers was considered friendly and welcoming at the beginning of that migration peak, the atmosphere changed to a restrictive narrative advancing hostile arguments against immigration processes, nourished by conservative and right-wing policy discourses and media amplification. The changing attitudes got manifested in a massive rise of the right-wing politics in Austria, and the subsequent participation of the right-wing party in the government (starting from the end of 2017) together with a conservative party that had already incorporated and was boasting itself of the realization of a restrictive migration and integration policy as their main political achievement

While the history of the aggravation of immigration regulation can be dated back to 1991, when the Asylum Act was adopted, the 2018 amendment to it can be seen as a clear recent expression of mainstreaming and tightening of migration regulation. This policy amendment aimed at extending the possibility of implementing a fast-track procedure for withdrawing the granted asylum status from refugees in the event of voluntary recourse to protection in their country of origin or acquisition of lost nationality. In 2019 a strong, more symbolic signal of re-naming the “reception centres” into “departure centres” showed the intention of the right-wing party being in governmental responsibility at that time to prove immigration in Austria as very difficult (DerStandard 2019). Main aim was to stem against entry of possible asylum seekers and not show any sign of pull incentives. With the new conservative-green government the term was removed again. In the past few years, in certain areas of integration an increase of duties for TCNs and a focus on sanctions, if duties are not fulfilled, can be observed. This notion relates to the perception of integration as a two-way process. In the Integration Act of 2017 (§2 para. 1 IntG) “integration” is defined as a process whose success depends on the participation of all people living in Austria and is based on personal interaction. It

states that integration requires that immigrants actively participate in this process, take advantage of the integration measures offered and recognize and respect the values of a European democratic states.

With the Education Reform Act the pressure on successfully and fast language learning for pupils with a lack of knowledge of the teaching language German has been intensified. A centralization of integration measures is recognized as dominant and adverse trend within the implementation of integration measures. While accommodation and care for asylum seekers as well as language and orientation courses for all newcomers have been provided at a regional and local level before, often through low-threshold activities, the provision of language and orientation courses must be provided by the Austrian Integration Fund (ÖIF) since the Integration Act in 2017.

A series of relevant initiatives have been elaborated across the country, extending to rural regions as well, and providing numerous examples from the two Austrian MATILDE case study areas. Good practices seeking to contribute migrants' inclusion in the local society are led to a substantial part by local actors, voluntary associations and individual volunteers, associations and NGOs, and social-sector institutions, partly supported by public funds and administration. By curtailing "public services" the bulk of integration efforts is hence entrusted in this private field of social groups enhancing effective integration pathways. Many of these initiatives are short-termed, project-funding dependent and conditionally approved as long as political support is not withdrawn. The long-term challenges of integration can therefore hardly be met in a sustained and empowering way by these structures and fragile conditions. Examples of good practices from the two regions include (For details and more examples, please see Austrian section in MATILDE D 3.1/4.1):

- Both in Carinthia as well as Vorarlberg an integration prize has been adopted by the Federal State Government with the aim to honour local stakeholders contributing to the advancement of social cohesion and bringing to forth good practices.
- A Regional Coordination Office for Integration aims at combining integration efforts of 11 municipalities and provides a regional anchor point for advice and support for migrants and refugees in this area.
- The Integration Pass of the City of Villach aims explain the local and national rules and customs to asylum seekers to facilitate their entry into society. It is divided into seven modules in which the conditions for living together in Villach are explained and people are given the opportunity to exchange ideas with specialists.

- A specific project targeting at a local welcoming society in a rural context was advocated in the project *Vorankommen* (Eng. progressing) indicating the aim to advance with integration objectives at this level. Through institutionalizing the approach it is expected to provide an incentive to shift attention and acceptance towards newcomers in small communities.
- In the rural Hermagor region, *Gekommen, um bleiben* (Eng. Come to stay) project aimed at raising the awareness of the public administration and the population towards migration process and raising pluralization of society. It served to create a service offer for immigrants according to regionally agreed quality criteria and thus make an important contribution to diversity and quality of life in the region.
- The Day of Encounter (*Tag der Begegnung*) in Carinthia is an annual event designed to strengthen polylogue and inter-religious understanding between Catholic, Protestant and Muslim religious communities.

In **Bulgaria**, the recent policy changes initiated at a central governmental level have failed to meet the local needs; that is, to mitigate depopulation and revitalize local development by utilising migration as a resource. Local migration and integration policies remain under institutionalized, and local authorities lack the tools to implement the national local policies effectively. Education policies were assessed positively because of the complementarity of factors and actors: governmental policy for enrolment of refugee children; active commitment of teachers for working with both the foreign and Bulgarian children for an inclusive education, as well as with parents who fear the migrants; active support of local NGOs. Housing policy has been less successful. The main actors are real estate entrepreneurs and NGOs supporting the most vulnerable migrants. Targeted local policies are lacking. In all, three main types of actors contribute to migrant inclusion in local society: 1) local and national level NGOs with complementary expertise, 2) churches by providing humanitarian assistance, and 3) migrant communities in their role as mediators and providing social capital.

Good practices include: 1) migrant empowerment. Successful examples of individual migrants who have managed to advance their social mobility despite difficulties, and now utilise these experiences to provide support for other migrants in vulnerable positions. 2) Charity events raise awareness and seek to convert hatred into solidarity. The Bulgarian report highlights successful campaigns and activities of solidarity, integration, and intercultural mediation and understanding.

These efforts have urged the locals to change the ideas and attitudes they may have held and come to see migrant that in a different light.

In **Finland**, the national legislation and the related policies are applied quite differently in the two studied regions, Ostrobothnia and North Karelia. In Ostrobothnia, integration of migrants is more geared towards employment and contributing the society through labour, whereas in North Karelia social integration is prioritised over the economic one. Migrant's well-being and welfare is supported by public policies in both regions. The municipalities are offering counselling for migrants, although in North Karelia these are rarely present as specific services. The municipalities organize immigration courses, including language teaching, in co-ordination with the private sector and various NGOs. These services have seen a hit recently due to the on-going Covid-19 pandemic. In North Karelia, the role of the third sector in TCNs integration is more significant than in Ostrobothnia. The third sector has an important role in organizing services and activities for migrants, especially for the TCNs. When regional economy and labour markets are weaker, social aspects of inclusion and integration, as well as the significance of NGOs in these terms, tends to get in turn emphasized. In the Ostrobothnia case study region, the TCNs integration is evidently more based on labour market integration, which is the most valued form of migrant integration according to the public policy discussion as well. Still, too often the discussion about migrant integration is limited on labour market activity and language skills while the social and cultural aspect are dismissed as less important and beneficial.

One of the weakness of Finnish integration policy is that it often targets refugees and other non-working migrants only, while other migrant groups remain out of its scope. The Finnish welfare state functions in a way that the responsibility of basic service provision rests largely on the shoulders of individual municipalities. Based on the municipalities' integration programs, it seems that the way integration is conceptualised, and the related services prepared for in a particular municipality depends greatly on the size of migrant population in that municipality; difficulties in implementing the policies in practice arise in rural municipalities where the number of migrants is very low. In these cases, the municipal integration programs are generally very simple and basic, suggesting migration and migrants' integration not be high on the agenda and that the time and resources invested on the related concerns are scarce. Nevertheless, the conducted interviews indicate that migrants are seen predominantly as having a positive impact in addressing the demographic challenges in rural areas. There is thus a mismatch between the perceived impact and the investments made towards migrants' integration and well-being in the local communities.

An effective integration process also demands the public, private and third sector actors to work flexibly together. The third sector plays an important role in improving the social and health services for migrants. They could play an even larger role as actors and mediators in enhancing migrant networking with each other as well as with the rest of the population, but also as organizers of leisure time activities. Resources are scarce, and while there is a need to rethink the financial premises and allocations for those organizations involved in service provision, other options for gaining further resources should be considered as well. The opportunities, which practices of social entrepreneurship, for example, could provide, are seldom considered. Despite the positive results of the few existing examples thereof, the customary trust on state being the primary resource provider remains strong.

As a good practice stemming from the Finnish case, its multicultural orientation can be mentioned. While expected to learn the local language and habits migrants are simultaneously also encouraged to maintain and keep developing their native language and cultural skills. In primary education, the municipalities are obligated to provide teaching in the first languages, as well as religious education based on one's conviction if there are enough pupils of the same language group or religious group in the school. In North Karelia, for example, Russian speaking pupils can have teaching in their mother tongue in their own schools. The two-dimensional integration is a good tool to foster a multicultural society, where both local/regional inhabitants are welcoming newcomers and migrants can integrate into a new society without abandoning their own cultural capital. Multiculturalism can provide a strong positive impact for the increasingly international labour force and the society as a whole.

Secondly, the practice of organizing integration services together in larger municipal consortiums has been growing, and become, especially in Ostrobothnia, also a common custom. Municipal consortiums allow sharing of resources, and avoiding any overlaps, by extending the organization of services aimed for immigrants beyond the borders of a single municipality, which gives the service provision much broader shoulders.

Thirdly, in North Karelia, the network of several NGOs working in migrant related issues, compiled together by the North Karelian Society for Social Security, can be seen as a successful example of pooling knowhow and expertise. The North Karelian Society for Social Security is an association which coordinates various kinds of migrant-related activities from social issues to anti-racist work. The network also covers public actors such as municipalities and the police. It is important to engage migrants themselves in the local and regional integration process and as members and

leaders of associations. When migrants themselves are actors in the integration work, potential problems of migrant objectification can be better avoided.

In **Germany**, the statutory social security system does not differentiate between Germans, EU-migrants and TCNs. Recently, a variety of policies on federal, Länder and municipal level has been implemented, which aim at the integration of TCNs. Yet, in a broader understanding of integration, i.e., inclusion into the society and participation, those measures had an indirect effect on migrants' impact on the German society in general. Positive effects can be concluded from the establishment of various new positions in the public administration and in Third Sector Organisations, which foster social integration of newcomers of refugee background but also aim at empowering them. The latter is reflected, for instance, when it comes to empowerment and knowledge transfer, e.g. in terms of establishing a pool of lay interpreters for recently arrived migrants. However, the positions are bound to the duration of the funding schemes and are thus only limited in time, even though integration is addressed as a continuous task.

In the social realm, the importance of volunteers must be highlighted, especially in small towns and villages. Despite general critics on the neoliberal outsourcing of social inclusion of immigrants to civil society, the 171 proliferation of volunteering activities, e.g. as refugee relief groups for this specific target group, contributed to the mobilisation of local communities. However, it is unclear how sustainable this development is. The fields of action of both civil society and local administration encompassed the access to housing and mobility as well as the establishment of meeting opportunities. The latter is crucial to diminish prejudices and becomes most effective once the wider local population can be involved.

Recent immigration trends unravelled challenges associated to the specific structures of rural housing markets as well as discrimination processes in terms of access to housing. For the specific group of asylum seekers, decentralised accommodation, even in peripheral locations, was a common strategy to mobilise vacancies or take pressure of the housing market, while courses for tenant qualification and rental mediators supported the acquisition of appropriate private accommodation (Weidinger & Kordel 2020). Specific policies to regulate relocation, i.e. the Residence Rule is mostly evaluated positively by stakeholders, since it offers a better predictability to plan and implement integration measures on-site and more easily warrants minimum amounts of participants. On the other hand, the Residence Rule is evaluated negatively as it leads to a reduced labour market integration and a limited access to the private housing market. The identified good practices include:

- The Association for Intercultural Work in Bavaria (*Verband für Interkulturelle Arbeit in Bayern e.V.*) hosts a Network for intercultural opening of rural districts and municipalities in Bavaria. It aims at fostering intercultural opening, welcoming and recognition culture as well as integration management especially in small and medium-sized towns and rural districts, drawing on information material, counselling, staff training, seminars, and conferences for local practitioners.
- The small town of Hofheim in the rural district of Haßberge in Northern Bavaria proactively engaged with the topic of refugees and nominated a Commissioner for Asylum even before the first allocations of asylum seekers in 2014. Together with the six other municipalities of the intercommunal alliance Hofheimer Land and the newly founded refugee relief group, they organised accommodation and addressed the specific needs of asylum seekers by means of providing lay language courses and lifts to courses, supporting recognised refugees to find appropriate housing, making use of an existing vacancy monitoring, or matching migrants' skills with the labour demand of local enterprises. Also an "asylum coordinator" has been hired to draw on successful measures of the rural development and reused them for asylum purposes. The Hofheimer Land provides a successful example of a rural area seeking to establish a welcoming and staying culture and to foster intergenerational and intercultural participation. A demigrantization is encouraged by applying a whole-of-society approach.
- The Integration Council Oberallgäu (Integrationsbeirat Oberallgäu e.V.) with its 177 members is the "voice" for migrants' interests in the rural district. It aims at establishing and retaining good relationships between local inhabitants and individuals with a migration history, at supporting migrants in socially, culturally, and educationally challenging situations, and at capacity building. As a result of the Integration Council's attempt, in 2001, the rural district administration created the position of a Commissioner for Migration and Integration, which was staffed with the chairwoman of the Integration Council. Together with a working group, the Commissioner launched an annual integration monitoring, an annual naturalisation event and an integration conference as well as an integration plan that defines the most important fields of action. To provide respective offers for migrants, the implementation of the integration plan is underpinned by an integration fund.

In **Italy**, the dynamics of social integration in mountain and rural areas appear less complex than in urban and metropolitan contexts: the relatively small numbers of people, the possibility of face-to-face interactions, the persisting communitarian dimension, are all factors that to a certain extent seem to limit the possible social tensions between old and new inhabitants. Yet, as the most critical cases of the reception system for refugees and asylum seekers show, social integration is only possible where civic and collective participation dynamics are activated. In the absence of this, the risk is as much that of the creation of separate communities living in the same territory as the possible manifestation of conflicts, often provoked also by xenophobic political forces, coming from outside the contexts considered. Therefore, innovative tools are needed to foster migrants' real participation in the social life of local communities, overcoming institutional forms of the past and developing different channels of involvement, focused for example on shared care of the territory or on the promotion of forms of socio-economic cooperation between new and old inhabitants, as the community cooperatives.

Although migrants represent an indisputable resource for rural and mountain economies and societies, policies for the re-launch of these territories usually do not focus on the role of foreigners to fight depopulation and population ageing, to maintain essential services in remote areas, to foster social and cultural innovation processes. In Italy, there is a general lack of policies to revitalize internal areas, just as it would be necessary to invest in active demographic policies to counter the decline that is affecting many mountainous and rural regions of the country. The demographic theme and the issue of territorial inequalities must therefore be put in relation with migration policies (and new peopling, more in general), within a vision of development of the country centred on a mutual relationship between the centre and the peripheries, and between the different populations living in these territories.

The Covid-19 pandemic undoubtedly represents a new threat with respect to the prospects of inclusion of migrants in rural and mountain regions, both in economic and labour terms (they are in fact among the most fragile categories affected by the economic crisis), and with respect to ghettoization phenomena (this is the case of asylum seekers forced to stay in remote locations) and possible intolerance or open racism (in the face of political forces that identify foreigners as a scapegoat). More than ever, therefore, action is needed to combat these phenomena, within the framework of more general policies aimed at fostering the resilience of rural and mountain communities, including the foreign component. The identified good practices include:

- The integration-and social work of the House of Solidarity in Brixen (South Tyrol) offers housing for migrants/refugees and local people in difficult situations. Three employees and 15 volunteers are involved in the initiative since 2002, which hosted 120 vulnerable people every year and satisfy their basic needs. They do that without public funds, bureaucracy, political, religious, or other dependence.
- HIPPY programme aims to support parents with children from 3 to 6 years old living in the territory of the Isarco Valley (South Tyrol) and provides services particularly to families with a migration background. It seeks to promote equal training opportunities for children, strengthening their language skills, the support of their cognitive, motor and socio-emotional development and cultural inclusion regardless of the children's belonging to a specific social stratum.
- InterAzioni in Piemonte 2 was an AMIF project carried out in Piedmont region in cooperation with other private and public entities. The project aimed to answer the needs of people of foreign origin through a strategy based on the coordination of different policies, including the adaptation of school system to multicultural contexts, the increased accessibility to services for integration and the strengthening of information services through territorial channels.
- In 2014, the Ministry of Labour and Social Policies and the CONI (Italian National Olympic Committee) signed a Programme Agreement for the implementation of activities aimed at fostering the integration of migrant citizens through sport and at combating forms of discrimination and intolerance.
- In Ormea (Piedmont), the agricultural and community cooperative *La volpe e il mirtillo* (Eng. The Fox and the Blueberry) was founded in 2018 as a result of a reception project that was initially opposed by the local population. Over time, these results have cooled residents' anger and suspicion towards immigrants. The project provided a path of integration in the green sector with the funding of a "community cooperative" that currently employs TCNs with the national employment contract in agriculture.
- Unitedbz is an integration project for the education of refugees and asylum seekers in South Tyrol. The Project was born in 2016 on the initiative of professors and employees of the Free University of Bozen-Bolzano, in collaboration with institutions and voluntary associations in South Tyrol that deal with the processes of reception of migrants. It gives asylum seekers and refugees the opportunity to attend the courses offered by Unitedbz

for four semesters, sitting its exams as extracurricular students, i.e., students who are not regularly enrolled in the university.

In **Norway**, the understandings of integration, and policy measures for integration, has come to largely focus on labour market inclusion over the last decades – much in line with tendencies in most other western European countries. However, as the economic and social dimensions of integration are largely overlapping, the understanding of integration should pay attention to a broad range of policies. The shifts in research and policy discourses in which employment and labour market inclusion is increasingly equated with integration, tend to shadow that integration embeds several interlinked dimensions. Employment can provide important means for social inclusion, but employment may not always be accompanied by social inclusion, and social inclusion may also take place on other arenas. This becomes especially evident when studying integration in rural and remote areas with less employment opportunities and in which access to social networks become especially important. This is reflected in the expert interviews which highlight the importance of involving civil society and volunteer organizations in integration work. Involvement in volunteer organizations and associations can give access to important networks and ‘bridging’ social capital and reduce feelings of isolation in remote areas.

Research also points to the importance of bringing together resources in the third sector with the formal programs and measures implemented by the government. Municipalities where the public services establish formal collaborations with volunteer organizations, produce better results from the introduction program compared to those that do not have such collaboration (cf. Djuve et al., 2017). There are, however, still relatively limited studies focusing on the role of the third sector and especially the importance of collaborative relations between government agencies and volunteer organizations, and the conditions for and impact of inter-sectorial and inter-organizational collaboration represent an important knowledge gap. The Norwegian team highlights the importance of considering integration in a broader perspective. In the Nordic countries in which the government takes a major responsibility for integration, activation of resources in the third sector is highlighted as good practice.

When the **Spanish** social policies are analysed, it is possible to visualise a theoretical integration of immigrants into the welfare system. Theoretical, because registered immigrants are in practice often subject to institutional xenophobia stemming from civil servants’ lack of knowledge about welfare

system benefit entitlement requirements. The principle of standardisation guarantees equal access to the system's benefits, yet in practice integration is limited to documented immigrants (naturalised or not), and partially to registered undocumented immigrants. Social policies on housing, emergency economic benefits and periodic economic benefits (i.e., Minimum Insertion Income) have met primary needs residually and insufficiently.

The situation and needs of each immigrant are different. The papers they have determine the way they can settle in the territory. Seasonal workers – with temporary work permits for the first sector – tend to settle outside city centres, in the outskirts; this implies that they are physically cut off from the rest of the population, making it very difficult to deal with institutions and the public administration, such as social services, and with third sector organisations. The spatial segregation has repercussions on social and cultural integration processes.

The reception policies promoted by local authorities – and partly implemented by third sector organisations – have a direct impact on integration processes. Firstly, because they provide immigrants with the main tool: literacy in the region's language. Secondly, because the advice they get helps them to understand their working environment, legislation, education and training, social and health care, etc. Thirdly, policies to facilitate the integration of foreign minors into the school system take a two-pronged approach: adapting the children to the educational system and providing guidance on how to live a multicultural society. Fourthly, there are a set of outreach and coexistence-oriented policies devised to improve interaction between the local population and immigrants. These policies have not solved the spatial integration issue as the use of public places remains stratified, preventing effective integration. In general, social integration is limited to a process of inclusion that stems from the development of an organic solidarity, based on a reciprocal need: economic dependence, in the primary productive sector and in the service sector, especially in care services; and demographic need.

Social and spatial inclusion in rural and mountain areas needs to be designed in a way that considers not only their population's diversity, but also the existing territory and communication infrastructures, as well as the orography of the terrain and the climate. In this respect, the Aragon Regional Government, with its Comprehensive Plan for the Management of Cultural Diversity in Aragon, 2018–2021 has laid down the general principles that should govern all the strategies: equality, standardisation, globality, interculturality, integration and accessibility. The social integration policy highlights include awareness-raising policies like the first Aragon Anti-rumour and Anti-

Discrimination Strategy, 2020, the Campaign against Racism and Xenophobia, and the educational policies oriented at everyone involved in the cultural and language integration of different individuals.

Third sector organisations need to be active in rural environments to be able to resolve issues specific to these regions, and of migrants at these regions, more effectively. Social acceptance, and therefore migrant integration, is easier in rural areas; however, it would be necessary to have more help in these areas to solve their problems. The analysis has also spotlighted a need to give civil servants ongoing training on immigrants' rights when they apply for welfare system resources. Setting up immigrants' associations in rural environments should be encouraged and immigrants should be encouraged to join or take part in local social fabric associations, as this would facilitate joint social dynamics.

In the wake of the 2015 refugee "crisis," **Sweden** has become a less-welcoming country for asylum seekers. It has become more difficult for the forced migrants to obtain permanent residency and to bring their family members. Anti-immigrant sentiments have intensified, which is illustrated by the rise of the Sweden Democrats party. However, despite the unfriendly context of reception, Sweden continues to provide generous welfare benefits for immigrants. Once a TCN has obtained a residence permit, he or she has the same right to welfare services as Swedish-born persons. This social security net, as well as a high quality of life, continues to attract immigrants to Sweden. The number of asylum seekers has, however, declined considerably since 2016.

Sweden is facing several migration-related issues. One of the key policy challenges concerns the housing situation for refugees. Many municipalities have struggled to provide accommodation within two months after a person has been granted a residence permit, as they are required to do by law. In addition, the newly implemented housing law has had unintended consequences. Municipalities who want to welcome more refugees are not allowed to do so, while some municipalities try to relocate refugees who have been assigned to them. In addition, refugees tend to move away from their initial place of residence, especially if they were placed in remote locations with high unemployment rates. Over time, they tend to move to cities, settling in low-cost housing areas where immigrants are over-represented. This is also the case for refugees who arrange their own housing. A new law aims to discourage refugees from settling in residentially segregated areas by withholding their benefits.

Three centre-periphery challenges in migration governance became identified in the field work. First, larger municipalities tend to allocate funding for staff who work with migration issues,

while smaller municipalities are less able to afford this service. The imbalance in staffing contributes to inequalities in funding and reimbursement between larger and smaller municipalities. Staff members who work on migration-related issues tend to be more informed about funding opportunities and reimbursement rules, generating revenue for larger municipalities that are already better-funded. Second, the settlement of refugees in rural areas has helped to offset population decline, and generated funding for schools, shops, bus lines, and other local services. The closing of reception centres in rural areas, as a result of the decline in the number of asylum seekers, is likely to negatively affect the provision of services in rural areas. Third, migrants may experience a lack of high-quality services in remote areas and may have to travel to access these services. Another policy challenge concerns language education. While many Swedes speak English, Swedish language proficiency is necessary for many types of employment. Municipalities offer Swedish for Immigrants (SFI) for all non-Swedish speaking residence permit holders, free-of-charge. The quality of the language courses, however, has long been an issue of concern, particularly in the smaller municipalities.

In Sweden, the national government funds most social policies, allocated at the national scale, and distributed to agencies at the regional and local scale. Municipalities oversee language courses and civics courses and are financially responsible for refugees if they are not self-sufficient after the two-year establishment period has ended. Regions are in charge of healthcare services and transportation, and the county and administrative boards play a coordinating role in the delivery of services and allocation of resources. This system requires a large bureaucracy and coordination efforts, with some gaps that voluntary organizations try to fill in. These efforts tend to be more prevalent in rural areas, but asylum seekers and refugees may experience social barriers in joining these organizations. The covid-19 pandemic has turned Sweden's gaze inward, as has been the case in many European countries. The primary concerns are now about health and the high unemployment rate. The integration of immigrants currently receives less public attention, except for media attention to immigrant criminality and residential segregation.

Turkish welfare regime, similarly to the Southern European model, regards the family as main actor, with different informal supports structures. Still, the state, with its unitary character also plays an important role as employer and services provider. Although the current situation in Turkey can no longer be treated simply as an emergency with respect to Syrians, humanitarian assistance programs and the implementation of different policies and projects are still provided in sense of emergency

support in the public view. Competition among the most vulnerable groups with respect to social assistances and job opportunities in the informal labour market create tensions. The increasing anti-immigrant attitudes are not, however, only a result of this threat perception. Although with the temporary protection status, the rights are legally defined, still access to these rights is limited with the existing conditions in the field. Not only in terms of availability of resources, which is crucial, but also the perception of people at every level is important for developing and implementing policies for harmonization.

Humanitarian assistance programs are still provided in sense of emergency support for Syrian refugees in Turkey. The role of the public sector has increased especially in social assistance and health care. Despite the vagueness of their specific mandate towards refugees, or non-Turkish citizens broadly, municipalities also take active role. Local authorities cooperate with civil society organizations to provide free services and orientation to Syrians about education, health services, and training opportunities. To overcome financial constraints, actively engaged municipalities seek external funding through establishing partnerships with NGOs and international actors.

Local governments have no legal, financial, or political-administrative responsibility and authority, yet they are still important actors in the field. Schools are crucial for current and future social cohesion, however, the conditions such as income and education levels of Syrian families, employment status of parents and language ability play a role in immigrant children's school participation. Similarly to the competition among the most vulnerable groups for receiving social assistance, the schools that are mostly populated with children of Syrian families are located in most disadvantaged neighbourhoods and have limited resources. To realize the goal of inclusive education, there is a need to support schools at every level, from supervision to teachers to curriculum change.

Right to health is crucial, considering the vulnerabilities and existing risks even before COVID-19, thus particularly those Syrians who work informally in seasonal agriculture or in other sectors, most of the time work in other cities than they are registered. The risks one faces by going to a hospital might seem to be more than by living with an illness and/or not getting health care. COVID-19 already puts enormous pressure on the available resources to health, including health workers. Another aspect to be underlined is the claim causing great tension that Syrians enjoy more rights and that they, without payment, have access to healthcare, whereas citizens of Turkey must pay more. Non-Turkish citizens, mostly Syrians, are regarded as scapegoats; they are to blame for the unemployment or insufficient social support. Overall, Syrians are still not accepted as permanent part

of the current and/or future society in Turkey and this dominant perspective influences policy making and policy implementation. Thus, it is urgent to develop short, middle, and long-term strategies for harmonization and the policy-making process should also be inclusive.

The following two projects can be seen to serve as good practices: “Health for Rural, Support to Rural” Project for refugees (Ministry of Health and UNFPA). Language barrier and lack of information are some of the key deterrents to the access to the right to health. Here, health mediators can be given as an example of good practice, as the right to health does not guarantee access to the right. Health mediators, chosen from the Syrian population, do not only provide translations but also act as a mediator to solve communication problems and reduce socio-cultural barriers. The Project on “Promoting Integration of Syrian Children into the Turkish Education System” is a project in education sector/an education project implemented by the MoNE with a view to contribute to the access of Syrian children to education provided in state schools /to education. It is funded by an EU grant within the scope of the Facility for Refugees in Turkey (FRIT) agreement. The project was launched in October 2016, and it is still in operation in 26 provinces. Within the large scope of the project, supports are provided to children, families, and schools in a variety of forms as well as cross-cutting services such as social cohesion activities are enabled.

In the **United Kingdom**, as assimilationist turn with a larger attention on migrants’ acculturation and an impact on the resources for ethnic, national, and religious community can be observed at the British level, at Scottish level an approach based on the importance of minority groups and recognition of multiculturalism prevails. On the one side, no integration policies were described except those aimed at refugees and asylum seekers, while the other categories of migrants were considered part of the national inclusion framework. On the other side, anti-discrimination policies seem to aim ethnic and national groups that can be described as “visible minorities” and diversity seems valued by the national as well as local government.

Consequently, a narrative of migrants’ valuable impacts for Scotland – notably from a demographic and economic point of view – is nowadays widely shared. As main integration policy, the New Scots strategy seemed to have provided a very important framework for understanding the path of the newcomers in the Scottish society and how to accommodate and integrate differences. Considering the limit of being a very recent policy without any deep analysis already carried out, the New Scots seems to have positive outcomes on migrants’ lives and migrants’ impact in Scottish society. With the “integration from the day one”, it contributes to avoid the limbo of asylum seeking

and its effects on the refugee integration potential we explored in the literature. It has a positive impact on the cooperation of different actors aimed at building a coherent integration model. Providing a narrative on refugees' integration, it contributes to the voluntary adhesion of all the Scottish Local Authorities to the resettlement program that allow refugee population to safely settle around the all country – the programmes saw very few out-migration toward urban areas and very few tensions – the fact that the resettled refugees were families with schooling children has been indicated as a key element for the integration in the new community.

This programme brought new challenges to the local communities in terms of perceptions and practices. Small and close communities welcomed people of different cultures challenging their own perceptions and practices as well as those of the newcomers. This brought for example a wide transformation in the way the local authorities deliver services bringing a larger attention to inclusion through e.g. translation of official documents in other languages and using interpreters. It brought along an encounter with new cultural praxis and new cultural traits challenging the fear of losing the “island way of life” or “diluting culture”. From a demographic point of view, “dying communities” have been happy to welcome a new population, notably if composed by children and families. Nevertheless, the link between services and migrant population seems still problematic – as resources and services change and the migrant population is likely to settle in the “centres” of the remote areas. As a good practice, a Community Sponsorship Scheme has been introduced by the Home Office as civil society wished to play a greater role in refugee resettlement, and with the expectation that the community-led approach will lead to positive integration outcomes for refugees and communities.

Comparative findings of the quantitative analysis on the social impact

Since the 1990s, **Austria** has been affected by significant migration inflows that took place within a broader international context, resulting in considerable effects on Austria's population structure and the socio-economic situation of both, the native population, and the migrants themselves. For the two last decades the positive international migration balance has contributed to a balanced and in parts even increasing population number in Austria, also in most of its rural regions. Despite the

preference of immigrants for larger cities, particularly Vienna, almost all rural and mountainous areas witness an immigration surplus which, in most regions, is sufficient to compensate for local population losses due to negative natural population development and losses in internal migration balance (Machold & Dax 2019).

These developments bear significant effects and come with strong implications for societal change fostering a variety of people of different origins, languages and cultural backgrounds intermix with the host society. While some of these effects, such as increasing cultural mixture and societal diversity, are becoming considered increasingly more positively by local population, migrants, in particular TNCs, remain generally marginalized in terms of many key indicators. Regarding situation in the two considered Austrian regions, Carinthia faces a slightly negative population development, a median income below the Austria average, one of the highest unemployment rates and structural problems, while Vorarlberg has a very positive population development, one of the highest income levels in Austria, an unemployment rate below the Austrian average and faces a prosperous economic development (cf. Aigner-Walder 2018).

As there is a relatively close correlation – and a causal link – between education and employment, people with lower education levels experience a significantly higher likelihood to become unemployed. This observation places the link between educational and labour market policies at centre stage, raising the need for enhanced public policies. The educational attainment level has a positive impact on the income level. Thus, the gaps between TCNs and the reference group considering the educational level led to implications in the poverty rate, the equivalised income and the overcrowding rate in immigrant households, revealing important target fields for policy tasks. The difficulties experienced and exposed through the indicators underline the importance to go beyond “traditional” migration policy which often tackles very specific areas of “integration” of migrants, not considering adequately the links between social and economic dimensions as delineated above. The goal of social inclusion for integration processes is therefore severely endangered due to the social gap as expressed by these indicators. This contributes to polarization processes, even in regional contexts with quite favourable economic performance. Such developments jeopardize social cohesion efforts.

The ability for active participation remains limited for many TCNs due to their reduced income and education levels and perspectives, and personal efforts are concentrated on achieving affordable personal conditions to access basic services. The question of citizenship is of relevance in this context, as specific employment opportunities, e.g. in the public sector, are not open to non-nationals,

and political participation is severely restricted. As outlined already in the policy report, demands for fulfilling the basic aspects of life have risen in recent years while forms of deeper integration have in turn retracted. Looking beyond the average picture is an important aspect to validate this, and to assess the meaning for different groups and the variability among TCNs, as well as to identify and develop innovative action to overcome these challenges.

The **Bulgarian** case study shows that in general terms immigrants are quite well integrated into the host society. However, the state of affairs cannot be credited that much on any effective government policies, but rather on the immigrant's own proactive projects and practices. Bulgaria's approach to integration is classified in the last MIPEX 2020 issue as "equality on paper", whereby many documents have been produced, yet often without any practical consequences on the ground. The collected material suggests that migrants in Bulgaria enjoy basic rights and security, but not equal opportunities. Major obstacles remain in nearly all aspects of life. Spatial differences between urban-rural were also reconfirmed in realms where vulnerability based on ethnic origin or gender play the main role. Discrimination and negative stereotypes remain frequent and socio-economic as well as cultural factors continue to contribute to the marginalization of migrants within the society.

The role of the regional and local authorities in migrant integration appears insignificant in Bulgaria. Furthermore, the potential for social cohesion which could stem from furthering migrant access to the regular aspect daily life were not seen in any levels of the analysis. Rather, there is a potential for negative trends in particular with respect to such social-economic indicators as risk-of-poverty, overcrowded household, unemployment rate, early dropouts, which in the Bulgaria are closely linked to ethnical background shows potential to be linked also with some vulnerable migrant groups present in the country.

The findings from **Finland** suggest that social protection as well as active participation and social rights display positive development, i.e. a convergence between TCNs and natives. The differences regarding being at the at risk of poverty have decreased particularly after 2012, and the net income for TCNs has increased comparative more than that of the native population. At the same time, however, social cohesion and access to and quality of services display negative development. The divergence trend in the social cohesion dimension appears as the most troublesome as low education is likely to increase the risk of unemployment. As the Finnish labour market is relatively knowledge-based, the relatively low educational levels of TCNs make it more difficult for them to

enter the Finnish labour market. Unemployment rates have an onward impact on both the housing situation and the income situation. Since 2010 the overcrowding rate for TCNs has increased significantly, which indicates a decreasing access to services. Overcrowding in housing for TCNs is related to lower incomes and a marginal position at the labour market. Nevertheless, the relatively well-functioning social security system in Finland ensure that many TCNs experience a relatively low risk of poverty compared to many other countries.

When assessing the general trends, it is important to keep in mind that the share of labour migrants and students is very high among the TCNs and so are the share of immigrants who have come to Finland for family unification reasons or as tied movers. Aspect such as social protection and right as well as options for active participation are of importance in attracting the mentioned immigrant groups. A closer look at the MSDs for social cohesion and access to and quality of services reveals that for labour migrants, students and tied movers to the aforementioned groups as well as to Finnish nationals displays a relatively high social cohesion and access to and quality of services. At the same time, other TCNs, most notably asylum seekers and refugees, struggle more with social mobility and the related hierarchy; that is, they face considerably more challenges with being included in the Finnish society.

The statistical data collected from **Germany** suggest that especially the arrival of forced migrants in the mid-2010s led to a temporary increase in social polarisation. More recently, a convergence has been detected. Immigration of TCNs, especially of but not limited to forced migrants, translated into a polarisation in terms of levels of qualification of TCNs (educational attainment) and a temporary slight increase in unemployment rates. Overall, however, both educational attainment and unemployment rates of TCNs developed positively and resulted in a convergence. The share of young people neither in employment, nor in education and training as well as the general migrant unemployment rate were on a constantly higher level compared to the overall population and rose temporarily following the arrival of forced migrants. Both indicators showed a positive development and a slightly converging trend. The number of residents who acquired citizenship decreased after the arrival of forced migrants in the mid-2010s due to lacking minimum requirements, and, similarly to the share for EU immigrants, remained on a low level over time. Nonetheless, TCNs may also be very active in civic life and participate in society without acquiring German citizenship (cf. Laine & Rauhut 2020, 29).

In **Italy**, a significant difference was observed at the national level between the share of native-born citizens and TCNs at risk of poverty. While the share of the first group remained considerably stable and low, the TCN population showed greater vulnerability to global shocks, their share fluctuation greatly in the given period, highly impacted negatively by the financial crisis of 2007–2008 and its aftermath. Seemingly unaffected by the global crisis, the income of the Italian-born population has steadily grown but of the TCNs stagnated, thus resulting in a slight divergence and a growing inequality of income between the two groups between 2004–2019. The overcrowding rate among immigrant households is on average 20 percent higher than of the native population and it shows a slightly growing tendency between 2009 and 2019. The tendency is alarming as the rate of overcrowding is one of the most fundamental social indicators; it affects health conditions, social integration, and the overall well-being of individuals.

A noticeable difference is apparent between the Italian born and TCN population with less than secondary education both on the national level and in the studied region of Piedmont. While the former showed a steady negative tendency, the share of TCNs remained relatively increasing throughout the examined period. In South Tyrol, the overall tendency of Italian citizens' share was negative and of TCNs' positive, however, with a much less accentuated trend than in Piedmont. In all, the gap between the Italian born population and TCNs has growing since 2014. The share of young people (15-24) neither in employment nor in education and training (NEET) has varied more; it increased in 2007 with more than 8 percentage points but has since then been picking up slowly. On the regional level, both in Piedmont and in South Tyrol, the share of native-born population NEET was below the national average and showed an overall slight increase.

On the national level, the unemployment rate of both social groups increased significantly in 2011 and has been picking up slowly. Similar tendencies can be seen in Piedmont and South Tyrol, although in South Tyrol the Italian born population has not been affected by the negative impact of the economic crisis and their unemployment rate remain relatively low and constant. The number of TCNs who acquired citizenship in Italy has fluctuated annually considerably, yet with an overall increasing trend. In all, the main tendencies of social indicators to given socio-economic groups can be greatly varied. The research conducted in Italy supports the general MATILDE hypothesis that the geography, regional economic differences, and vulnerability to global shocks all play key roles in the lives of TCNs.

In **Norway**, being at risk of poverty is an important indicator for social polarization: the non-EU28 immigrants in Norway are at a much higher risk of poverty than the majority population, both at the national level and at the regional levels in Innlandet. Being outside the labour market leads to lower income, which in turn limits the individual's opportunity to take part in activities in society. This also has consequences for the living conditions of immigrants, as housing costs make up a considerable part of living costs in Norway and the proportion of people living in conditions of overcrowding are higher among immigrants than for the remainder of the population. In rural areas, the labour market is weaker than in more central areas that tend to offer more employment opportunities for people with limited education and limited formal qualifications. Such opportunities might encourage jobseekers to move towards more central areas. At the same time, however, several factors counteract the pull of employment opportunities in more central areas. Housing costs are for example higher in more suburban/urban areas and can thus represent a barrier for moving to more central areas as financial restraints can make housing suitable for a family inaccessible.

Many of the municipalities in Innlandet County are struggling with issues related to having an aging population as the younger generations leave in the search of education and employment opportunities elsewhere. To counteract this development, refugees are being settled in these municipalities, and to finance integration, the municipality receives financial support from the state. However, there is a tendency that the economic schemes for integrating migrants are not applied in a way that sufficiently ensures employment opportunities for migrants in the region. Consequently, the level of secondary migration is higher among job-seeking immigrants than it otherwise could have been, had there been employment opportunities available to them in their settlement municipality. Reduced labour market participation can also lead to increased expenses for the municipality, as they are required to cover social welfare and other forms of financial support. The migrant thus becomes dependent on the public sector for support but is not given the opportunity to get themselves out of this dependency unless they choose to move, in which case they do not contribute to the desired local development.

Social cohesion within a community is affected both by the extent to which migrants take part in the local community, their social mobility, and whether they can improve their economic situation over time. The second-generation immigrants have a significantly higher degree of social mobility when it comes to employment and partaking in tertiary education than first-generation immigrants. At the same time, we see a polarization within the group of second-generation immigrants, where on the one hand, there is a larger proportion of second-generation immigrants

who participate in higher education than the general population. The share of NEETs is higher for people with an immigrant background than for the general population. Over time, this can lead to increased differences within the Norwegian society between ethnic Norwegians and people with a different country background.

In **Spain**, the migratory reality has become ever more complex: the circumstances and origin of immigrants who settle in Spain have varied, and so have the reasons / triggers for migratory processes, among which family reunification has gained importance. This urges us to adopt a comprehensive approach when assessing the effects and opportunities of migratory flows, since not all people of foreign origin fit well into the category of “immigrants”. There are important differences in income and wages between Spaniards and the rest of the nationalities. The greater relative vulnerability of foreigners in the Spanish labour market is shown both in terms of salaries and in the higher incidence of underemployment and unemployment. This also explains the differences in the material living conditions of immigrants and natives, as well as the greater risk of the former of belonging to the group of the so-called “working poor” and of suffering from situations of poverty and social exclusion.

Housing plays a fundamental role in social integration, precisely because of the multiple functions it performs (protection, socialization, coexistence, etc.). The guidelines of the residential model of immigrants are closely linked to their socioeconomic situation, their activity and work integration. However, there are other factors apart from the housing market that also affect access and quality of accommodation, such as the rapid quantitative increase (in number), their diverse nationality, the different causes that intervene in their migratory project, or the time of residence in Spain. Greater residential stability is linked to the family project, the constitution of a family and especially the arrival of children, are key factors in the search for a larger residential space and a more conducive residential environment. In general, many indicators show the highest residential exclusion of foreigners, mainly non-EU citizens, and especially in certain nationalities; However, the official sources of information do not allow knowing to what degree these circumstances correspond to initial stages of the migratory processes or to those with worse residential conditions.

Another characteristic analysed is the difference between the structure by qualifications of the workforce of immigrant origin and that corresponding to the autochthonous population. The educational level attained continues to be a major factor to explain the differences in the incidence of unemployment, and even with nuances, the workforce of immigrant origin has an average level of

qualifications lower than that of the native population. The analysis of the labour situation of foreigners TCNs points to an unfavourable position in the labour market, concentrating on non-qualified occupations. In addition, excessive temporary employment, and involuntary part-time work, and even underemployment can be observed. However, all these positional tends to improve over time – even in the crisis context.

However, in terms of integration, there is one group that has benefited more than the others: Latin Americans. The arrival of the Latin American population and its rapid assimilation by comparison with other immigrant groups also entail frustration among and exclusion of immigrants from other countries. This applies especially to Moroccans who arrived earlier and who saw the glass ceiling of social mobility being significantly lowered when they were replaced in the niches they had occupied by workers from Latin America. It is important to note the divergence between the homogenising pan-Hispanic rhetoric wielded by politicians and actual migration policy where, apart from differential access to nationality, personal situations and labour market characteristics are given higher priority than one's origin. Despite the positive situation in terms of integration, there are other factors that still hinder the integration of foreigners, favouring inequality. An example is the toughening of the laws regarding the authorization and processing of documents to be able to work in Spain and the difficulties for the renewal of permits that make them immersed in an irregular situation on many occasions.

In **Sweden**, similarly to the other assessed countries, the group of third country nationals can be seen as special in more aspects than lack of citizenship in Sweden (or having been born there). It is well known that TCNs are younger, show a male surplus, speak Swedish to a lesser extent, and their educational profiles differ from those of the Swedish population in various aspects. Thus, the general figures fail to capture the extent the deviations within the TNC group. The Swedish report points out that as a concept citizenship has another meaning in Sweden than in most other countries: due to the Swedish citizenship policy, the group of third country nationals consist, to an unproportionate part, of newly arrived immigrants as their predecessors tend to have been acquired a citizenship. With this said, the third country nationals or immigrant population are worse off than the native population in almost every respect. They have less income, shorter education, higher unemployment rate, higher NEET rate, and higher overcrowding rate. The situation is similar in North Central Sweden (including Dalarna County), except for tertiary education. Neither are there any signs that the gaps are closing. If anything, the message is rather a tendency towards the opposite.

In **Turkey**, the overall dominant perspective does not accept immigrants to form a permanent part of neither the current nor future society in Turkey. The focus of the Turkish case study has been on Syrians, whose access to rights in Turkey depends on their registration to a particular locale. Syrians with temporary protection identity cards from a particular city face difficulties in accessing opportunities elsewhere and even prefer often to be unseen as they do not want to be sent back to the city where they were registered in. Even with work permits, requested by prospective employers, immigrants are allowed to work in the province in which they are registered. The application for work permits time consuming and costly and needs renewal every year.

The informal economy in Turkey also is an obstacle in this sense, while at the same time the livelihood of Syrians also often depends on this informality. Informal labour usually leads to precarious and exploitative working conditions endangering the wellbeing of immigrants, including from child labour to work-related accidents. The vast majority of TCNs work without work permits and outside the protection of the law, with low wages and without access to social security. The region of Bursa, a rural area with high agricultural production and textile production, is attractive for both seasonal agricultural workers and textile workers, both of which operative largely on informal basis and relies on low paid workforce with migrant backgrounds.

Poverty and social exclusion remain as fundamental challenges in Turkey, and the Covid-19 pandemic has only caused further risks for vulnerable population. The wide gap between the haves and have-nots persists in Turkey, along with regional gaps. Research conducted in different parts of Turkey demonstrate competition among the poor with respect to social assistance and informal labour that leads to tension rather than social cohesion. Unemployment has also been a serious challenge for a long time in Turkey. Over recent years, the increase in the unemployment rate among the foreign population can generally be explained by the arrival of the Syrian population to Turkey. However, this does not mean that the inflow of Syrian migrants in the labour market has a significant effect on the overall unemployment rate. This is mainly because an overwhelming proportion of the migrant workers are still employed in the informal sector, despite small procedural regulations providing rights to them to access to the Turkish labour market.

Turkey has the highest NEET rate among the OECD countries. This can be credited to several reasons such as political and socio-economic problems caused by polarized politics, child labour, gender-related inequalities, giving up hope on finding jobs as well as migration have multi-layered effects on youth wellbeing in the country. The mismatch between young people's skills with the

needs of the economy also explains the high level of NEETs. Regarding migrant youth, the high level of NEET mostly refers to the arrivals of millions of Syrians to Turkey, and not to be well integrated into the job market as well as into the education system.

In the **United Kingdom**, the TCNs are overall considerably more likely to be at-risk-of-poverty than UK and EU citizens. In particular, the Great Recession of 2008–2009 affected significantly more and for a longer period TCNs than others to the point that in 2010 one in three TCNs were at the risk of poverty (double the UK nationals). This has been linked to their limited access to welfare benefits than nationals such as to access a safety net in difficult times. The introduction of the Home Office “hostile environment” policy can be seen to have contributed to the worsening TCNs economic conditions by restraining legal opportunities for them to access decent employment. Given the post-recession recovery of the labour market and the related more employment opportunities for TCNs, but also the effects of the Tiers Point-Based System aimed at allowing entry to the country to skilled migrants to fill qualified jobs, the new incoming TCNs workers have been notably more skilled and underrepresented in sectors that employ mostly routine or semi-routine workers. Comparing TCNs and EU citizens, the gap between incomes have increased progressively over the years and has its peak in 2017. EU migrants had overall similar incomes to UK citizens until 2017 when they started to have higher incomes than the local citizens. This can be understood as the effect of the Brexit impact on the type of EU migrants in the country and with the depart of many migrants working in routine and semi-routine occupations.

The gap between the share of UK citizens and migrants living in overcrowded accommodations remained large and constant for most of the considered time span – the overcrowding rate among UK-born people was mostly constant around four percent while for non-UK born was on average 15 percent. Overcrowding is more common in the private and social rented accommodations and non-EU and EU migrants are less likely to be owners (less than one in every two) compared to UK born people (about 70%). Overall, the indicators showed a significant gap between TCNs and UK and EU citizens, an issue that worsened during the recession period as well as in the most recent years.

Education is both a tool of the migrant agency and a mean for inclusion. The UK has attracted and/or allowed in a population with higher education than the UK-born, and UK’s university and higher educational system attracts international students. Differently, at regional level, the recent growth in sectors that require high skilled workers with tertiary education and the impact of in and

out migration. Education policies like ESOL and the work-based learning system have been described as important enablers for the migrant participation in the education system in Scotland. At regional level, even higher share of tertiary education among migrants is observed. The non-EU born have an initial higher rate of NEET (15%), but it decreased since 2008 and it is now equal to that of the UK born (about 10%). These similar relatively low rates among all groups in the recent years have been linked to the programs that Scottish government activated to contrast the phenomenon.

Overall, the indicators show in the last quinquennial a worsening of the social polarisation between TCNs on the one side, and EU and UK citizens on the other and increased obstacles to social integration. TCNs are overall more educated but they have lower incomes than UK and EU citizens. The presence of a common educational framework resulted of the Process of Bologna could be a key element to understand why for EU migrants' education and skills mean higher income, as the portability of the skills from the country of origin to that of arrival is a key factor in shaping migrants' opportunities in the labour market. TCNs have an even higher share of tertiary education than EU migrants but those skills are less likely to be recognised in the receiving country so that they need to rebuild both education qualifications and working experiences to access the local labour market (Baglioni & Isaakyan 2020). This may help to understand why high share of tertiary education among TCNs corresponds to lower income and higher risk-of-poverty.

Comparative findings of the qualitative analysis on the social impact

In **Austria**, drawing from the experiences of involved actors of main institutions supporting the integration process in the years of 2015-2016, an increased level of enthusiasm for welcoming refugees was broadly experienced across the regions and municipalities throughout the country. Voluntary support by local inhabitants spread at that period, which suggested a change towards swift inclusion and acceptance of immigrants (of all types) among most of the population. The period was illustrative of exaggerated expectations for “successful integration” processes which all too often encounter substantial difficulties at later stages. All over Austria, including the case study regions of Vorarlberg and Carinthia, support disposition subsequently faded away, expedited by regressive national support for migrants and the rise of a political discourse favouring hostile positions towards

migrants and neglecting their positive social contributions to local and regional communities and economic benefits to national economy. Nevertheless, particularly at local level, a strong commitment for integration objectives and practical support for inclusive strategies persisted.

The peculiarity of the case of Vorarlberg is that asylum seekers or at least one asylum-seeking family was accommodated in almost all municipalities, even in very small and remote ones. This made organization of professional care sometimes more difficult for the regional provider Caritas and has been reduced also due to fewer number of incoming people from 2016. Although a migration trend of people with a refugee background from the remote to the more accessible municipalities has been noticeable on a low regional level, between 2015–2016, the number of TCNs, who are largely composed of people with a refugee background, increased by almost 900 people in the rural part of Vorarlberg and has continued to increase slightly ever since then. Decentralized accommodation and the establishment of a network of local and small-regional support and counselling facilities in the valleys have made an important contribution to ensuring that population figures also develop positively in the rural regions of Vorarlberg.

Regarding policy perceptions, in both regions, the politicians adopted a view that swift, balanced and successful integration is dependent on focusing on the strengths of refugees, TCNs and all groups of migrants, thus seeing migrants' positive contribution to the local societies. Particularly, the former member of the Regional Government for Integration aspects in Vorarlberg is acknowledged as a “driving actor” for many activities facilitating implementation of support for migrants. That commitment is (still) beneficial to many actors in respective institutions to engage in activities to overcome integration difficulties that are rising with new policy regulations and increasing administrative challenges.

The narrative presented by interviewees largely exposes the potential for a linkage of positive social and economic impacts of integration. This assessment builds on the strong economic position of Austria's regions and the on-going demand for labour which cannot be covered by local inhabitants. In Carinthia, sectors such as tourism, would no longer be able to offer their services without migrant workers; some companies that have already had good experiences with migrant workers also keep asking for them at employment agencies such as IAM in Carinthia. Findings also show that the admission of foreign people to the employment force is inevitable which represents a good concomitant opportunity for social acceptance of migrants as well. While in the past qualifications were not as advanced most enterprises nowadays have increased the requested skill portfolios (Amann 2020; Buber-Ennsner et al. 2016) and a high bodily strength, work ethos and

commitment of new arrivals is no longer sufficient. Increasingly, German language skills are also relevant for industrial workers and matter as additional challenge. Slow adaptation and failures to show understanding of cultural diversity might have a significant rebound effect on hampering integration processes and acceptance among local communities.

Beyond work integration, a host of interrelated aspects are crucial for positive integration outcomes. This includes besides the core aspect of language learning, acquaintance with cultural unfamiliar features, expressed in housing behaviour, recreation organisation, family and community life, neighbourhood contacts, etc. A stumbling block is quite often the role of women including their retreat into the private sphere hampering social contacts with locals (also local women) and community. Most respondents are confident, or at least hopeful, that the next generation might adjust to living conditions and local norms and will call this area their “home” and a much higher level of inclusion might be possible for most of them. What is noticeable in any case is that second-generation migrants whose parents came to Austria, in particular, to escape war, and talked about returning to their countries of origin, have actually started families in Austria and have actually settled down.

Inclusion and social impact might remain very different for a long time, and there are few signs of social mobility from the first sight. Nevertheless, educational participation of young people with Turkish or Ex-Yugoslavian background is much higher than several years before, and participation in labour market, particularly for young females, increased. However, new arrivals often enter at the bottom of the social hierarchy, and with respect to social and emotional integration (cf. Esser 2001) resemble migrants who have arrived before from the lowest social position in society. Overall, supporting institutions struggle with coping with administrative obstacles to achieve first approval for temporary and then permanent residence permit, and later employment and social integration. This contrasts with the qualifications and skills of some of the migrants which are, however, hardly acknowledged and therefore prevent any rapid social mobility success. The more harmful effect is that this deteriorates the impression of incomers and favours dependence of TCNs, even over longer time frames.

When it comes to active participation, it is not easy for migrants to take active part in e.g. voluntary activities, as they must learn the German language first (compulsory by law, see § 7 and § 9 Integration Act), show great efforts to enter the labour market quickly and need to familiarise themselves with the new framework and living conditions in Austria. Nevertheless, in both case studies, Vorarlberg and Carinthia, TCNs have begun to engage in clubs and associations such as the

Red Cross, Caritas or football clubs. A few have also taken on leadership roles here. Besides official membership and participation in associations and clubs, results also show that migrants engage in helping other migrants, e.g. in mosques but also via voluntary or remunerate work in integration counselling organisations and projects. The empirical research, however, confirms that stronger efforts are needed by local/traditional associations and clubs to become more open for new, migrant members and show a welcoming culture.

In the **Bulgarian** case, the research conducted focused on the town of Harmanli in the Haskovo region gives a rather heterogeneous picture regarding the significance of place for migrants. For amenity migration rural spaces are considered as primary destinations, while for many of asylum-seekers the case is the opposite. The asylum-seekers are placed in the Registration and Reception Centre in Harmanli, though not by their own choice, but by the decision of the official in the host country. For family migrants, place is of secondary importance, the determining factor being the ability to starting a family.

The Bulgarian team report there to exist no competition between locals and migrants, for which the main reason is that there is no labour migration. The Haskovo region is among the poorest regions in the poorest country in the EU, whereby it is deemed as unattractive for economic migration. Amenity migrants have a higher living standard than most locals, and very few refugees reach the local labour market.

The social impact depends both on the temporality and the volume of migration. The sudden, significant increase in the number of migrants after the opening of the refugee centre in Harmanli was experienced as a shock. The significant increase in the migration flow following the establishment of the Registration and Reception Centre in this small town initially had a negative impact for several reasons. The first is the big change in the ratio of locals to refugees, when the number of refugees grew to several thousand in a town with a population of fewer than ten thousand. The second is the initial unpreparedness of public institutions to efficiently manage the refugee crisis and reception of asylum-seekers. The third is the local population's lack of intercultural experience in coexisting with large groups of migrants. The more gradual temporality of the settlement of amenity and family migrants, as well as their smaller number, contribute to their positive reception on the part of the local population.

The establishment of the refugee centre has, however, also had a positive impact. It has become one of the biggest employers in Harmanli, providing a variety of highly skilled jobs. Whereas

the radical increase in the number of refugees had a negative impact, giving rise to fears and apprehensions among the local population, after the situation calmed down their impact began to be seen as positive because they boosted local business, such as grocery stores, restaurants, and banking services. In all, the migrants' presence in Harmanli and in the surrounding region can be characterised as coexistence, rather than cohesion. Despite numerous practices for bridging migrants and locals live parallel lives. There is one positive exception: family migration.

Social inclusion follows different trajectories. It is the lowest in the case of transit migration – for most refugees, the region is a short stop along the way to Western Europe. The most comprehensive and multifaceted is the social inclusion of family migrants. Family migration is a steppingstone to labour migration as well as to inclusion in the family, neighbourhood, and local communities. In-between the two poles – of non-inclusion because of transit migration and full inclusion because of family migration – are the amenity migrants, the largest number of whom are British. Noteworthy also are the success stories of integrated and empowered refugees – entrepreneurs, interpreters, cultural mediators.

Women are autonomous and active actors. A specific characteristic of family migration is that it is mostly female, most family migrants being women from Russia and other post-Soviet republics. Most of them are successfully integrated in education, business, medicine, or services. Some women amenity migrants are active in volunteering to provide help to refugees, especially refugee children. The case with women refugees is more specific. They often need support to find work as well as social and humanitarian assistance for their large families.

Place matters. Key factors for the territory's attractiveness – a fine climate, high quality of life, clean food, peaceful way of life, comfortable homes with gardens, good connections to big cities, closeness to Greece and Turkey – were appreciated before the pandemic too, yet the perceived value and attractiveness of remoteness has become emphasised in (post)Covid times. The advantages of the territory are found particularly attractive by the amenity migrants, but also those Bulgarians born in the region, who have studied and/or worked in other big cities in Bulgaria or abroad and now seek to return to the region. The return may be either temporal, consisting of remote work from home, or permanent. Many have renovated their family houses and used them for self-isolation during the pandemic, but also for holiday homes, and/or even for future longer-term residence. The dynamic tendency of growing interest in the attractiveness of remoteness, which started before the pandemic but was intensified by the latter, is one of the interesting findings of this study.

The two case study regions in **Finland** have quite different regional profiles, whereby they provide an illuminating perspectives and specificities on the impact of migration that is often discussed on a more general national level. In North Karelia, most of the population is Finnish speaking, while in Ostrobothnia the Swedish language, also an official language in Finland, is widely used. The economic structures of the regions are also different. In North Karelia, unemployment is high, and the service sector is a major driver of economy, while Ostrobothnia's economy is an export industry oriented. In North Karelia, the municipalities are more rural and similar to each other, apart from the central city of Joensuu, while in Ostrobothnia, the structure of municipalities differ greatly from each other. North Karelia also has a rather homogenous migration population, Russian speakers being the dominant migrant group. Russian speakers are moving to the area mostly for family and education reasons and less so because of work. In Ostrobothnia, the migrant population of the region is diverse and many TCNs are moving into the region as labour migrants.

In both the regions the possibilities in the labour market and existence of co-ethnic community are key factors in permanence of stay. Most of those who came as refugees or asylum seekers move out of the regions to larger cities in the south of the country after their integration period is over. The phenomenon is especially apparent in North Karelia, but it also happens in Ostrobothnia. Together with better job opportunities, a key factor helping the migrants stay in the region is the language. If the TCNs are integrating into Finland in the Swedish language it creates both advantages and disadvantages. The Swedish language increases agency in rural parts of Ostrobothnia and helps one's integration at least in the Swedish majority areas. It is also said to be somewhat easier to learn. Minority populations being relatively more welcoming towards newcomers who pick up their language and culture is a rational behaviour: each newcomer who joins them will increase their relative size. If the TCNs are aware of this, picking up Swedish will smoothen the life in the new country and especially in Ostrobothnia. On the other hand, if TCNs cannot speak Finnish it limits their opportunities to move, work and study in the other parts of Finland, but it can also limit the possibilities inside Ostrobothnia as parts of region and some major companies use Finnish as their main operating language. The integration process in Swedish can help in finding work in the area, but at the same time, it can hinder one's possibilities elsewhere in the country. However, there are long-established migration flows between Ostrobothnia and Sweden when it comes to Swedish speaking Finns. Learning Swedish in Ostrobothnia provides a viable Plan B: if one does not succeed in Finland, proficiency in Swedish will open the labour markets not only in Sweden but also in other Nordic countries.

In North Karelia, the overall unemployment level is high, one of the highest in the country. This creates a tendency for migrants, just as it does for the natives, to move from North Karelia to the other regions of the country, where the labour situation is better. However, there are sectors in labour markets, which do need work force. These include care, agriculture, high tech, and the service sectors. For this reason, the regions existing labour market situation should be carefully evaluated and the education paths, mainly the secondary and tertiary education, should be focused so that TCNs could be educated to those sectors where there are employment opportunities. This would both impact the local labour markets but also help immigrants to integrate and settle down into the region better. However, we cannot expect all the immigrants to educate themselves for the labour market sectors which are locally lacking, but the bigger international picture of labour markets must be taken into consideration as well.

The impact of immigration can also be seen from the perspective of everyday security. The bridges between “old inhabitants” and immigrants are not always easy to construct. While the everyday life, in terms of interaction between local dwellers and TCNs, of studied rural regions seems to largely go on smoothly, many immigrants, especially the “visible” migrants, face structural and everyday racism. Action has been taken in this regard as respectable interaction between immigrants and locals is promoted and active anti-racism is paid attention to in both the case study regions. The third sector plays a crucial role in this as much of integration and multicultural work is done by NGOs. While migrants are integrating into associations which are run by the locals there are also some NGOs run by the migrants themselves. It is highly important that immigrant run organizations are promoted and encouraged and immigrants are let in on the decision making in local public and third sector organizations. There are also many types of activities which are not especially organized for immigrants, but where they are actively taking part in and impacting local and regional communities.

A phenomenon where everyday security should be considered by public policy more efficiently is the mental health issues of TCNs. The treatment – the lack thereof, that is – of traumas and other mental health issues of asylum seekers, refugees and other immigrants forms a key problem in the Finnish integration system. The contemporary treatments and support processes are not enough, and more education and resources should be focused in the area. In most extreme cases uncured mental health problems can cause other societal problems. An introduction of more occupational forms of therapy in TCNs’ mental health treatment could provide a step forward and be more effective than traditional therapy treatments. The mental health issues need to be taken

seriously as they come always with societal and structural elements as well rather than just individual ones. Neglecting their treatment can have a major negative impact on society.

The social impact of TCNs for the studied regions is noticeable also in secondary and tertiary education. In both regions there are educational institutions, which benefit greatly from TCN students. Some of these units have strategically built up their activities around TCNs. Their strategy under the reforms of Finnish education system have been the internationalization of their work. As the Finnish educational network has been reduced, condensed, and centralized this has been a key coping mechanism for certain educational organizations, especially in more rural areas. Some of these units would likely not exist anymore if they did not have international students.

For the rural areas both in North Karelia and Ostrobothnia the presence of immigrant population is creating vitality in everyday life. Immigration also alleviates the deteriorating demographics of the regions. The street scene has become more multicultural, and this was appreciated by our informants. There are, however, also many for whom the multiculturalism brings discomfort or may even present a threat. If immigrants integrate into Finland and especially into its remote areas properly, this will have a major impact for those regions and the county. It is a fact that rural areas all over the Europe, but also in Finland, suffer from demographic challenges and, in addition to the workforce, immigrants are having an impact on this as well. There are many young people and families among TCNs, and it is precisely those demographics who are needed in rural areas. For them to adapt and settle in these areas, a range of support mechanisms, guidance, and social contacts is required.

Lastly, it is important to underline that different immigrant (groups) have different ways of integrating into rural areas: some are tightly integrating into their own language groups (e.g., Russian speakers), some integrate more with the local communities and their set up networks with Swedish or Finnish speakers (especially those who come from rarely spoken language groups), and there are those who integrate into English speaking multicultural communities (typically highly educated). In working towards liveable everyday life and multiculturalist society, all these should be equally appreciated, and there cannot be one proper way of integrating. There are several ways of having an impact as well. The university students' better integration into more rural regions is one unsolved problem, which should be further considered. As most tertiary jobs are mostly in larger cities, this is a difficult task to undertake. International university students could have a major impact on the regions and their economic and social life through more efficient integration.

In **Germany**, the social impact assessment provided a first glimpse into realms affected and subsequently transformed by the arrival and settlement of TCNs. While a welcoming culture was reported in the MATILDE region of Bavaria after 2015, polarization of the society arose in parallel and the open and inclusive notion after the arrival and settlement of forced migrants was challenged. For a sustainable and rooted understanding of an inclusive society at rural places, various actors, sometimes also encompassing local elites, at certain localities make tremendous efforts, while, at other places, diversity is met with disregard. For social cohesion, opportunities for interaction, facilitated by mediators, were identified as key in the MATILDE region of Bavaria. By enabling encounters, the attitudes of the resident population could be changed partly. However, cohesion is challenged by a hierarchization of immigrants as well as conflictive interactions within the migrant communities.

Active participation of TCNs is mostly visible in terms of intercultural and inter-religious activities. While such an involvement might be event-like, a more continuous participation is realised by involving immigrants as volunteers, e.g. as lay interpreters. Becoming engaged in local associations is reported quite rarely and, consequently, rural societies seem to be quite fragmented. Reasons for a lack of participation are mutually dependent and simultaneously individual (e.g. lack of time, lack of language competencies) and related to the attitudes of the society sketched above. Regarding access to and quality of services, TCNs in rural and mountain areas created new jobs and infrastructures, first but foremost in the social sector. Counselling activities are present in all rural districts under study, while the access for immigrants is hampered because of family-related obligations, language barriers or restricted everyday mobility, while their legal status is often treated pragmatically. Having acknowledged such barriers, local stakeholders overcome them by, for instance, providing childcare, lifts, or a tenant qualification. Positive social implications are observable when actors continuously learn from immigrants' life-worlds, identify barriers, and adapt and modify their offerings. Moreover, a continuation of infrastructures must be realised and is also desired in the rural districts, since they fear a cutting of funding due to decreasing number of arriving immigrants or because of the COVID-19 pandemic.

A possible strategy for a continuation of social infrastructures would be a demigrantization and a mainstreaming of jobs and services, i.e. from target-group specific to whole of society-approaches (Dahinden 2016; Papademetriou & Benton 2016). Simultaneously, stakeholders (use their room for manoeuvre and) make efforts to include migrant groups that are less visible, like EU-immigrants or even locals, as they often face similar problems in rural areas. Related to this issue, the

communication of immigration as an opportunity for the region must be improved, also drawing on the regional identity and history of the region. General acceptance in a region can also be fostered by inter-municipal networking, while the involvement of politicians or larger employers in general must be strengthened, e.g. inviting them to round tables or discussions. To increase the engagement of TCN newcomers, recruiting strategies for local associations must be intensified, against the backdrop of ageing, especially for young people. Besides, bottom-up activities of immigrants should be supported. The interaction between immigrants and locals could be strengthened, without neglecting the special need for social inclusion of immigrants and forced migrants in particular. Finally, encouraging immigrants to stay in rural and mountain areas and encouraging a place-based belonging is considered as prerequisite for sustainable and long-term positive implications of TCNs. By doing so and highlighting the opportunities in rural areas, regional and local stakeholders could counteract the prevailing assumption of rural areas as ‘transient places’ for immigrants.

In **Italy**, a substantially heterogeneous picture emerges regarding both the characteristics of the investigated territories of South Tyrol and MC Turin and the types of migrants present in these regions. The analysis confirms the importance of the dimension of place when considering the social impact of migration in rural and mountain contexts, evidencing the role of path dependency for these processes, and how the local assets of resources and constraints (linked to local history) have a strong influence on them.

The two territories under investigation, South Tyrol and MC Turin, show very different capacities in terms of migrants reception and inclusion: South Tyrol is an economically flourishing region, with a well-established rural and tourist economy and few demographic problems (mainly related to ageing trends), while MC Turin is an economically and socially fragile territory, characterized by a weak rural economy (highly fragmented and showing an uncertain future) and a tourist economy that has difficulty in taking off on its own; in these valleys, the demographic problems are dramatic. The needs expressed by the two territories are also different: in South Tyrol an increasing request of mainly manual and low-skill workers, while in CM Turin rural and mountains areas seem to need first the revitalization of villages and their repopulation, contrasting demographic decline and dismissal of essential local services.

Facing these different and place-based needs, and considering opportunities and threats for inclusion and social cohesion, three main categories of migrants arise in these territories: the “migrant in transit” (more present in CM Turin), whose migration project does not foresee a

permanence and a rooting in local territories; the “settled migrant” (more relevant in South Tyrol), who is interested in a life project even in rural and remote areas; and the “temporary migrant”, who could implement strategies of (partial) rooting at local level, following the flow of seasonal jobs elsewhere, but having in mountain areas a sort of a centre for his/her residence. The change of socio-economic status for these different types of migrants seems possible, but it is made difficult by excessive bureaucracy and constantly changing national migration policies, which often modify the abovementioned local assets. The lack of legal channels for migrants to enter Italy by means of a simple work permit, represents the major obstacle for any local or regional policy of social inclusion, while it has a dramatic impact on the concrete possibility of rooting for migrants in rural and mountain region, as in metropolitan ones.

Even among economic and Labour migrants, the mountains or rural spaces are rarely considered as primary destinations. Many migrants come from urban backgrounds and are more attracted by larger cities, where they see more opportunities to work, and options to socialize and meet with others. Most migrants have a traditional approach to the countryside and agriculture, whereby they do not see the advantages that new technologies and innovation could bring to the rural/mountainous world. Their value system appears very far from the one evoked by the Italian “new highlanders”, who choose the mountains in search of an alternative lifestyle.

The analysis of the two local contexts shows that between newcomers and local people there are essentially functional relations, based mainly on the recognition of mutual usefulness, moving from the labour market needs and offer. While this instrumental dimension of the social world represents the basis for a wider interpersonal and socio-cultural recognition regarding the different communities, by now it seems that non-instrumental relationships involving migrants are mainly ethnically or religiously based. This prevalence of ethnicity seems also not to allow migrants, as a supra-ethnic category, to have a real political weight within the considered territories, prevailing closure or even separation, within the different communities. In the analysed rural and mountain areas, there is no real competition between newcomers and locals for access to resources. Migrants work, have lifestyles and live in places that are not attractive to locals. A kind of socio-cultural impermeability to local contexts seems to exist; conflicts are avoided but, at the same time, the migrants are not becoming rooted in these territories, nor are the different population groups living in the same space melting together. There are more disadvantaged groups within migrant populations, such as women, who constitute the most fragile category: for them, cultural (and even

physical) isolation, lack of social contacts and interaction with the local community often results in psychological disease, exploitation, and mistreatment.

Mountain and rural communities often show characteristics of social closure and parochialism that do not always facilitate processes of interaction with newcomers. They themselves appear poorly integrated, lacking in internal social cohesion. Mountain communities in the Metropolitan City of Turin appear exhausted by decades of depopulation, in which context, the rhetoric of populism – fostering the so-called revenge of the places that do not matter – takes root easily. The situation appears different in South Tyrol, where local communities experience a structurally two-faced and dialectic dimension, with a German majority and an Italian minority, which creates a complex and uncertain scenario for newcomers.

Social impact of foreign immigrants in rural and mountain regions can be enhanced - and, to some extent, even positively intensified, together with a strengthened social cohesion - by supporting the rooting of newcomers in these territories. If place matters, we need to avoid any spatial determinism. A sense of belonging to rural and mountain territories requires some basic conditions for the enactment of the local dimension by different population insisting on it. In particular:

- improvement of public transportation and welfare services, and more accessible and equal housing policies;
- reception projects tailored according to the size and needs of local communities, supporting widespread micro-hospitality and territorial development projects;
- bottom-up approach to local participation, enhancing local initiatives that bring together local administrations and associations/groups of citizens, while focusing on the effective agency of migrants as actors of local development;
- support to mutual exchange and cooperation between locals and newcomers, aiming at fostering a shared care of the territory in which they all live, and avoiding focusing on initiatives targeted only on some social categories;
- active listening to the needs and personal projects of the migrants arriving in mountain and rural territories, in particular to help some of the "highlanders by force" to become "highlanders by choice", rooting in local communities and developing their own ideas;
- adaptive training projects for migrants, capable to take into account the changes in local labour market, the opportunities, and how to cope with them in an innovative way;

- investment on cultural mediators, to be intended as agents of local development, supporting connections between different social worlds, and strengthening the system of mutual trust at local level.

The dominant narrative conveyed through the research conducted in **Norway** carries that immigration is expected to have a valuable or positive impact on rural communities. Immigration is perceived as valuable for it can help counteracting tendencies of population decline and, thus, keeping rural areas “alive”. The conducted interviews highlight potential positive impacts on the local economies; potential positive impacts in terms of enhancing cultural diversity and tolerance in rural areas; and it is seen to potentially help rural municipalities to sustain local service provision such as local schools. However, the informants also discuss a range of potential pitfalls, and they are concerned with how different kinds of integration measures need to be in place if immigration and settlement of immigrants from outside Europe will have the kind of positive impact that they envision. It is important to make this distinction between discussions of impact of immigration on local communities, and the impact of specific integration measures on integration processes. Integration, within the Norwegian policy discourse, implies that incentives are put in place that should enable immigrants to maintain their cultural heritage, but it also refers to the rights and obligations of immigrants to make efforts to become part of the new society. Overall, there are concerns about the multifaceted nature of integration, and about the broad set of resources required to make integration work locally.

Immigration, and settlement of refugees in particular, may have a positive impact on the municipal economy. However, also potential pitfalls exist. The municipalities receive funds from the state to cover expenses and investments when settling refugees. There is, however, a risk that the transfer of integration funds to from the central governments to the municipalities are not actually invested in the integration measures but are instead spent to cover up shortcomings in the other parts of the municipal budgets. With these strategies, rural municipalities run the risk that settled refugees move once the introduction period is over if they have failed to foster a sense of belonging and development of networks locally. If the municipalities fail in providing networks, skills and competence that could enable the refugees to be better included in the labour market, they are likely to move to other places in search for jobs.

While the funding is meant to be used for integration measures, across different organizational units and service sectors in the municipality, the funding is not earmarked in a rigid

and specified manner. The central government trusts the municipalities to make purposeful decisions on how the funds are distributed and spent, based on the reasoning that the decision makers in the municipalities know the conditions, needs and challenges in their municipalities the best. This system is in line with long traditions in Norway, with placing emphasis on local self-governance in the municipalities. The central government tends to grant the municipalities leeway to make priorities in line with their insights and understandings of local conditions and needs. This distinguishes Norway from for instance Sweden, which have a history of more centralized control. This is reflected in differences in how the introduction program to refugees have been administered and implemented in Norway, Sweden, and Denmark. At the same time, a new Integration Act (2020) has been implemented which has been valid since January 2021, and which replaces the previous Introduction Act (2003). The new integration act contains elements that downplay the local autonomy of the municipalities and entail more standardization and centralized control regarding the local implementation of the introduction program. The implications of this, when it comes to the impact of the introduction program for the integration of refugees, are yet to be seen and analysed.

Immigration to rural areas has the potential to enhance the level of tolerance and reduce hostility and resistance towards people that look different and have different customs and traditions. More exposure to cultural diversity is expected to lead to heightened levels of tolerance and acceptance. Thus, it is not anticipated that increased numbers of immigrants would lead to disintegration and increasing level of antagonism, but rather the opposite. Attitudes towards immigration and immigrants are likely to be shaped by the majority populations direct experience with immigrants, as well as with direct with the effects of demographic changes and local transformations. By concretely experiencing the impact of immigration as positive for rural communities, for instance when it comes to sustaining local services, more positive attitudes towards immigration and immigrants are seen to follow.

In Norway, integration has become the dominant policy strategy for managing difference and introducing immigrants to the new society. Integration policies place emphasis on the rights of immigrants to maintain cultural heritage, and to participate, but also on their obligations to participate. In the policy discourse, Integration is understood as a two-way process which require that immigrants make efforts and show willingness to become integrated, and that the host society are open to integrate immigrants and to put measures in place that may facilitate integration. Hence, the policy discourse on integration forms the backdrop for how the consequences or impact of immigration is discussed in Norway. Largely, integration is perceived as a process or means to an

end rather than an end (impact) in itself. Different kinds of integration measures are perceived as necessary means to ensure that immigration will have desired impacts, such as providing a better life for people in need, building sustainable communities in rural areas, building culturally diverse and tolerant societies, etc.

Integration as a policy strategy (cf. *vis-à-vis* as an analytical concept) differs from integration as measure or indicator of degree or level of immigrants' embeddedness in society. The main indicator used for measuring integration in Norway is labour market inclusion (and enrolment in education). This is set at the main performance indicator in the monitoring of the introduction program, the most comprehensive integration measures for immigrant refugees. The program is provided by the municipalities for refugee immigrants, who have the right to and are obliged to participate in this program. The aim is to ensure that 70 percent of the participants are in work or education after completing the program.

Whether labour market inclusion is a good indicator for measuring integration is a different question. As Norway is a country with high employment rates, exclusion from the labour market has broad implications in terms of exclusion. Still, a too narrow focus on labour market inclusion as an indicator of integration entails the risk of shadowing other dimensions of integration. Taking a more holistic approach to integration, exploring it along different dimensions, may reveal that at an individual level people may feel included and yield a high level of participation without being employed, and alternatively people may be employed but at the same time feel scarcely integrated or included, and may have low scores on other forms of participation. A related risk of mainly focusing on labour market inclusion as means and indicators for integration, is that other forms of measures may be neglected so that immigrants that are not eligible for work (for instance due to health impairment) become further marginalized and excluded because measures targeting these groups are not prioritized.

In **Spain**, the inclusion model proposed from the integration policies clearly establishes equal rights and opportunities for those who are regularly in the country. However, its implementation takes a bottom-up scheme from the local level. The municipalities – even the regions at the immediately superior level – have lacked the sufficient time to adapt to the increased demand for basic services for the population. Currently, these levels of administration lack financial capacity and technical support to develop them. However, the perception developed during these years about the need for institutions to adapt to the migratory phenomenon is a positive one, as part of the process of

demographic change and the economic model of the area. The difficulty lies in the implementation of the policies.

Entry into the protection system occurs through the administrative act of registration, regularization by roots, reunification of family members, etc. All are documentary processes require a registration of a home. The lack of suitable housing in rural areas makes it difficult to settle in smaller municipalities, whereby an adequate housing policy would be necessary to receive the new population in rural areas. Immigration has led to an increase in services in rural areas, which in turn has made an important contribution to the revitalization of rural areas. The new families' arrival to and presence in rural areas has made it possible to increase school places, conciliation services and activities related to intercultural coexistence. Other positive aspects of this process have been the coordination of public services with third sector entities, which has made it possible to cover part of the needs. In general, there is also a revitalization of civil society through participation in non-profit organizations. The difficulty in accessing vital opportunities related to physical and social wellbeing has led to the development of a more stratified rural society. Whether social polarization in rural areas is a temporary phenomenon or a structural fact with a permanent impact, remains to be seen.

Endogenous factors that facilitate full inclusion are related to the administrative situation of immigrants as well as social, cultural, and human capital. Considering origin as an analytical category, some immigrants, such as the sub-Saharan population and somewhat less the Maghreb population with employment as seasonal workers, have faced more difficulties in terms of social inclusion. The settlements outside the urban centres, their temporary nature, and the lack of family, prevents a greater relationship with the population, limiting the development of networks that help them in their labour insertion, facing other difficulties, and achieving a sense of belonging to a community.

There are also immigrants who arrive with greater integration potential; that is, with greater human and social capital as well as labour mobility and ability to access the resources that the host society offers them. Immigrants from Latin America, either economic migrants or under humanitarian protection, possess key cultural elements, most notably language skills, which allow an easier relationship with the native population and a better access to the labour market accompanied by more social progression. It is also easier for them to acquire new nationality and the related rights. The presence of an entire family (*vis-à-vis* an individual) helps to establish ties beyond their immediate internal relationships. Those with greater cultural capital stand out with faster upward social and labour mobility, as well as rapid socialization in the host society. In addition to the already mentioned lack of housing in rural areas, another endogenous factors, one determining factor that

hinder inclusion and integration is linked to the lack of public transport that hinders the access to services. This difficulty is shared by social groups - natives and foreigners alike yet felt the most by the less economically favoured and those with fewer networks and contacts.

In **Sweden**, the goals regarding migration and integration are formulated at a national level. These goals should then be implemented locally, but support to enable this implementation needs to improve. There is a risk that intentions get lost in translation since local prerequisites are so diverse, the room for interpretation is wide, and there is an unawareness on national level (the Swedish Migration Agency) of how local structures work. These circumstances can be summarized as: a dissatisfaction with how responsibilities are distributed; lack of a national strategy that applies at the local level, lack of a shared agreement on what the goal should be; and lack of communication between different sectors and levels (*stuprön*). A policy that exemplifies this is Gymnasielagen or the Upper Secondary Act. This law could be seen as a hindrance for integration and interviewees find it difficult to understand the societal purpose of investing a great number of resources in educating this target group when the conditions for utilizing their future skills look so bleak. They worry about their mental health and that they might end up living in a parallel society. The youths are much needed in the work force but the possibilities for them to find a permanent job within six months after graduating from their education is unrealistic.

There is a pronounced focus on participation in the labour market. To achieve this, one must work with the issue from two directions: migrant employability and the employer's treatment. In the case study region of Dalarna there has been a shift from initially emphasizing migrants' characteristics and skills to also including employers' opportunities to change their own structures and attitudes. Above all, good collaborations with the public sector are presented, the collaboration with the business community needs to improve and become more active. In some municipalities, the refugee migrants' contribution to the care sector is crucial for fulfilling the need of staff. Interviewees relate to their closest surroundings, relatives, and friends, and notice that it would have been impossible to offer the needed services without the migrants. Local cooperation between the municipality and the local labour market agency is important for reaching labour market integration. The employment service's declining number of offices contributes to complicating this work, and knowledge about the local labour market risks are weakened.

Immigration, in general, and the reception of refugees, in particular, are part of political goals that connect to other areas in policy and society. Even though migrants contribute to filling labour

market vacancies in the municipalities, the attitude towards migrants may be negative. This observation relates to other parallel processes such as an increased financial commitment for supporting individuals outside of the labour market and a decrease in public service in many municipalities. The public labour market agency has closed their offices in many municipalities, health care centres have been closed, libraries have financial difficulties and concerning private services, banking services is becoming scarce. State withdrawal may lead to dissatisfaction that will show negative attitudes towards migrants. From a municipal perspective, it can be perceived that the municipality in question takes its responsibility and contributes to meeting the national goals, but when it comes to meeting local goals, there is less support from state institutions.

Approaching gender equality in integration processes is complicated. The focus is placed upon labour market participation which can be seen as following an overall Swedish policy of dual-income households and access to public welfare that should allow for gainful employment. Migration to a new country means that gender relations will appear in a new context, they will transform, and they will be challenged (cf. Stenbacka & Forsberg 2020). For example, there might be a tradition of male breadwinners and women staying at home in the home country, a separation of men in productive activities and females in reproductive activities. It is possible to discern such assumptions also in contemporary labour market measures; men more often than women get access to labour market-oriented measures in their contact with the Swedish public employment service (Nordiska Ministerrådet/Oxford research 2018; Jansson 2020). As the Swedish model and provision of welfare is based upon a dual-income system, such household strategies as well as structural inhibitions not only complicate integration, but they also have a negative effect on the household economy. In addition, discrimination on the labour market on the grounds of gender and ethnicity needs to be addressed for migrant women to fully participate.

It is possible to discern two approaches towards reaching social inclusion: 1) emphasizing labour market participation, and 2) through civic engagement and social networks. Crucial for both approaches is the development of language skills. There are still no legal requirements regarding language tests, yet the newly arrived are obliged to join language classes to obtain financial support. Being engaged in association life is described as an important way to learn the language in a more informal way and to become familiar with social patterns and gain social networks. Social networks are essential also to access the labour market as many jobs in the region as well as in the country in general are distributed through social networks. The regional sports association in Dalarna addresses issues of the recruitment of practicing athletes, trainers, and board members; by scrutinizing the

associations actions and routines in their out-reaching as well as self-reflecting practices. Civil society activities are important, for social meetings as well as for offering activities aiming at strengthening certain competences. The role of the public sector, and all public (state, region, municipal) activities are however viewed as most important since they set the base for other initiatives.

In the **Turkish** case, the country is home to the world's largest refugee population regarding the presence of the high number of Syrians. However, the registered Syrian population, more than 3,6 million in figures, is considered under temporary protection in legal terms due to the country's maintaining the geographical limitation to the 1951 Convention. Therefore, the intensive policy-making process in the last ten years has focused mostly upon the policies and regulations on the Syrian population. Syrians are still not regarded as a permanent part of the current and future society. Difficulties experienced vary with respect to age, gender, and previous experience. With the pandemic, existent economic difficulties in Turkey increased and Syrians are there to be used as a scapegoat for continuous problems (cf. Uyan-Semerici & Erdogan 2020). The anxiety and the fear of the pandemic has only made the situation worse. Despite the improvements especially over the last five years in the fields of providing basic access to education, healthcare services, and to the labour market, the field research primarily points out the challenges caused by the "residence location" in implementation. Especially for the Syrians to whom foreign identification numbers are assigned, like all other legally resident foreign nationals, can utilize formal services only in their residence location. This basic requirement primarily has a direct effect on the scope of informal migrant labour. Since Bursa province is an important hub for agricultural, industrial, and service sectors, many migrants prefer to stay unregistered in the province to find a job. This prevents immigrants from enjoying their rights to reach public education and health services.

Some alternative implementations have been applied to substitute the disadvantages and to facilitate accessing services, especially in healthcare and social support. Health mediators who provide mobile services in rural areas with the coordination of international umbrella organizations are among these implementations. They do not only provide health services to registered migrants living in remote places and working in rural areas, but also services to those unregistered in the province and even undocumented. In terms of social assistance, both regional and local levels are more flexible to meet the needs of the migrant population residing in locations in their responsibility compared to central public administrations, sometimes by putting aside the formal procedures to help especially those in more fragile situation. However, the municipalities are still in need of

additional resources to compensate for the burden which puts extra pressure on their budget due to the increase in the regional and/or local population they must provide services for. Thus, the quality of services provided to the migrant population is primarily related to the available sources.

The language barrier is still a considerable challenge for migrant children at school age. This seem to cause them to stay behind the locals at the same age, and to have an impact on the schooling rate as well as being bullied at schools. With the emergence of the pandemic, the gap between local children and refugee children has widened further. The pandemic has also had a dramatic effect on migrant children who do not attend school in different regards. The support mechanism for children has been weakened in matters such as obtaining guidance service, detecting negligence or abuse, and health monitoring. There is a special need to consider the migrant population which still does not have any access to crucial services. Particularly for those residing in remote and rural places, informal communication channels make their access to information about the services easier. To imagine one's future in the society one is living in is vital for feeling secure and to imagine a common future for all the members who are living in that society is a symbol of social cohesion. However, in the case of Turkey, there is still a long way ahead, and acknowledging the political, social, and economic restrictions, mainstreaming the social cohesion for any and every project that is planned is necessary.

The report from the MATILDE case study in the **United Kingdom** discusses how migrants interact with local communities and public services in two rural / remote Scottish communities (North Ayrshire and the Outer Hebrides) and focuses on the mechanisms and opportunities that facilitate newcomers' inclusion in new societies. The report highlights that category of "migrants" need to be questioned and negotiated between the researcher and the actors involved in research. Being born on the islands, or living there for generations, and being able to speak Gaelic and to participate in the local community and culture define the "locals". Consequently, migrants include a wide range of groups - British and European migrants as well as TCNs - and such a wide notion of otherness prevails on more specific ones based e.g. on nationality, religion, or ethnicity. This approach can potentially facilitate social inclusion. Having children emerged as a key element facilitating migrants' inclusion, providing also an unusual (positive) view on how gender (being a woman and a mother) impacts on migrant's inclusion.

Participation emerged as a key enabler of social inclusion. Playgroups and other forms of parental organisations were frequently mentioned, together with volunteering. Volunteering seems

a key turning point for migrant access to the local society in terms of both cultural and social capital. On the other hand, volunteering is often aimed at the local community wellbeing – as in the case of cooking meals in foodbanks, working for the Citizen advice, etc. – such as migrants’ volunteering activities resulted in a benefit not only on migrants but on the larger society. In this sense, volunteering brings benefits for both the migrants and the local community.

Migrants’ civic participation is often challenged by the migrants’ needs – to work, to take care of family members, to participate in other activities such as English classes – as well as by hostile environments. The awareness of migrants’ stories and experiences – directly (in shared moments, like for the allotment’s volunteers) and indirectly (with the refugee children hiding from the plane) has changed the local perception, most notably in the case of the refugees. Participation in religious groups acted as an enabler of social inclusion because the volunteering activities were organised by religious organisations, or through migrants’ participation in local religious groups. With the example of the Western Isles’ Mosque, the arrival of few migrants empowered the local co-religionists’ needs (local Muslim population) pushing forward this religious facility project and how migrants worked together with local co-religionists as well as non-Muslims supporting the project, building ties with the local community.

Considering the issue of services, migrants’ role in retaining essential services in remote areas positively reflects on the sustainability of the community both in the short term – by allowing the service to run – and in the long term – by keeping those areas attractive for new potential incomers. Nevertheless, it was not possible to evaluate the proportional weight of TCNs and EU nationals in producing such an impact among all the newcomers. In terms of access and/or exclusion from services, important efforts have been, and are being, made at local authority scale to support vulnerable migrants in their access to health, education, housing. The skills built by local actors for the benefit of the Syrian refugees which can benefit other migrant groups and potentially also vulnerable locals are an asset to be preserved.

In summary, the factors strengthening social cohesion and newcomers’ social inclusion include the intertwined deployment of services and actions by local authorities (language provision classes, healthcare, socio-cultural events) and local communities (volunteering opportunities via religious groups and civil society organisations) as well as personal conditions (such as newcomers who are parents and therefore have opportunities to meet other parents at schools and education related events). The factors delaying inclusion consist of newcomers’ needs to earn a wage allowing sending remittances (which very often turns in long working hours which leave small space to

socialisation); language barriers which sometimes obstruct newcomers' access to locals and services such as specialist medical treatment (e.g. dentistry); unawareness of opportunities and services.

Towards enhanced social impact of immigration

This last section of the present report identifies and pulls together, in the form of a SWOT analysis, the key observations and findings from the work conducted with the WP 3 across national and regional contexts in order to better understand how TCNs impact varies across countries and regions and how it influences the social dimension of the receiving society. The summarising list below highlights the key strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats which arise from the conducted field work across the MATILDE regions. The list also includes the territorial aspect and indicates the county/region where the particular observation was made. It is important to note that the geographical specifications included in the list are not meant as an all-encompassing depiction. Rather, they indicate in which report the given observation stems directly from. While the WP 3 comes to an end with the deliverable, the work summarised here is by no means over. The work continues in the frame of the other related MATILDE work packages, to which the WP 3 has been intended to feed in, with the aim to develop innovative action and social innovation practices based on these findings, to utilise the strengths to overcome the weaknesses, and to tap into the observed opportunities to minimise the perceived threats.

Clearly, as hypothesized already at the beginning, a positive social impact of immigration on the host society occurs when immigrants and the integration of immigrants are perceived to add an extra value to the society, in particular when this extra value would not have been created without the immigrants. In turn, a negative social impact of immigration on the host society is evident when the opposite occurs. Targeted policies and migration governance seems to play a key role in determining migrant impact. In this regard, a message that came up in a number of case study reports was that more and better policy measures are needed to improve migrant integration, including administrative and financial resources. However, keeping in mind that integration is a two-way process and as such depends such a much on the host society than what it does on the migrant, the situation is evidently easier said than done. The careful balancing act is needed, as many well-intentioned programmes and policies aimed at giving special preferences to migrants and refugees have also been taken to downplay or even ignore the needs of the local communities (cf. Islam, Rohde

& Huerta 2019), in which the immigrants are expected to integrate to, nurturing is so doing the risk of exacerbating rather than facilitating inclusion. There are, however, a number of illuminating differences coming from different Matilde regions, which in turn support the main premise of the project: place matters. Rural and mountainous area have a lot in common, but they are not the same.

Strengths

- Multiform language courses as an integration tool (Austria)
- Home visits to build trust, help migrants in difficult situations and detect negative developments (AU-Carinthia)
- Diverse range of well networked NGOs and migrant support institutions (Austria)
- “Integration from the first day” approach ameliorates exchange between locals and newcomers and led in many cases to longer lasting relationships between both (AU-Vorarlberg)
- Family migration as a case of positive multiform inclusion: linguistic, labour, social, intercultural, etc. (Bulgaria)
- The Registration and Reception Centre for refugees (in Harmanli) a major employer providing jobs for a variety of highly skilled professionals (BG-Haskovo)
- Education integration of refugee children an inclusive policy with a positive impact on both the inclusion of migrant children and enhancing the intercultural expertise of teachers (BG-Haskovo).
- Diversity of the migrant population benefiting the everyday life and economic sector (FIN-Ostrobothnia).
- Increased diversity led to increased tolerance and created a well-functioning group relation (FIN-Ostrobothnia); Intercultural opening of society, a self-reflection about one’s own position because of encounters (GE-Bavaria)
- Russian speaking TCNs forming a cultural and social cross-border bridge between Finland and Russia (FIN-North Karelia).
- Attractive job market (IT-South Tyrol).
- Inclusive reception projects for asylum seekers and refugees (IT-MC Turin).
- Inclusive rural communities, positive interaction between locals and migrants (IT-MC Turin, IT-South Tyrol).

- No competition between locals and migrants in the job market (IT-MC Turin, IT-South Tyrol; Bulgaria).
- Civic engagement of locals for TCNs who were often not engaged before (GE-Bavaria)
- Civic engagement of TCNs (GE-Bavaria).
- Organizational changes and intercultural opening in administration (GE-Bavaria).
- Government's comprehensive investments in integration measures meant to work as a scaffolding and help immigrants take part in the labour market (Norway).
- Equal rights and opportunities through standardized access to protection system services (Spain).
- Standardized labour insertion for regular immigrants (Spain).
- Actions to strengthen cultural diversity and multicultural coexistence, school integration and adaptation programs in rural areas (SP- Aragón).
- Perception of the migration process as an opportunity for demographic change and the economic model (Spain).
- Immigration a part of political goals that connect to other areas in policy and society (Sweden). Public education as a facilitator of social inclusion and active participation (Turkey).
- Tendency to rethink/redefine the migrant and the juxtaposition between "us" and "them", can potentially facilitate social inclusion (UK).
- Having children a key element facilitating migrants' inclusion, providing also an unusual (positive) view on how gender (being a woman and a mother) impacts on migrant's inclusion (UK).
- Intertwined deployment of services and actions by local authorities (language provision classes, healthcare, socio-cultural events) and local communities (volunteering opportunities via religious groups and civil society organisations) as well as personal conditions (UK).

Weaknesses

- Language and digital barriers (Austria)
- Recognition of previous education being a very bureaucratic and time-consuming
- Detrimental impact of the Covid-19 pandemic: on social integration and cohesion: Restricted personal interactions, disengagement, withdrawal into local TCN communities (Austria)
- Cultural norms: Establishing contact difficult for women with headscarves (AU-Carinthia).

- Integration undermined by far-right parties and xenophobic anti-migrant political discourse, as well as by everyday racism (Bulgaria)
- Transit character of the refugee migration a challenge for the policies and practices of integration (BG-Haskovo)
- Discrepancy between the needs of the local labour market and the professional profile of most refugees (BG-Haskovo).
- Perceived general rural unattractiveness, trend to relocate to main cities (Finland)
- Unwillingness to integrate despite presence (e.g. students), limited (unused) impact on local development and vitality (Finland)
- Lack of housing facilities (IT-South Tyrol; SP-Aragón)
- Lack of job opportunities (IT-CM Turin)
- Lack of essential public services (IT-CM Turin; SP-Aragón)
- Fragmented social context due to ethno-linguistic policies (IT-South Tyrol)
- Weak relationship between urban and rural/mountain contexts (IT-MC Turin, IT-South Tyrol)
- Long-term social innovation focused only on the denser populated small towns, where TCNs concentrate (Germany)
- Welcoming culture (in 2015) only temporary and limited to forced migrants, social integration a long-term issue, currently also overshadowed by COVID-19 (Germany)
- Some local elites, e.g. politicians, rather inactive in terms of social integration of TCNs (Germany).
- National and standardized immigration strategy overly formal and bureaucratic, detached from grass roots actors (Norway; Sweden).
- Full time participation in the immigration program may cause immigrants to interact mainly with other immigrants only, becoming thus detached from the regular society they are supposed to become part of (Norway)
- Scarce investments are made in integration measures aimed at others than refugees and asylum seekers. This can create tensions between groups, and marginalization of groups that are expected to handle interactions with the majority population without extra support. (Norway)
- Geographical dispersal policy in settling refugees (Norway)
 - *Weakness*: persons that are likely to have challenges with being included in the labour market are settled in areas with scarce labour markets and few job

opportunities, which further weaken their preconditions for gaining employment and contribute to increasing social inequalities between immigrants and the majority population, with risks of increasing polarizations.

- *Strength* distributes the resources and the potential burdens related to refugee settlement equally throughout the country, support broader prioritizations in regional policies to maintain distributed settlements also in remote and relative inaccessible places.
- Lack of economic and technical capacity in rural areas to implement revitalization policies (Spain)
- Development of a model of seasonal economic activity (SP-Aragón).
- Little digitalization of administrative processes and in rural areas (SP-Aragón).
- Perception of migration as a temporary and discontinuous process (SP-Aragón; Turkey).
- Logic of “temporariness”: many programs and projects run as emergency support, hinder Syrian migrants becoming a permanent part of society (Turkey)
- Requirement of registration in the province of residence hinders the access to opportunities and social services (Turkey).
- Lack of contact result in a situation as “living as two separate groups”, where the locals and immigrants live in the same locality, region, country but with very limited contact (Turkey).
- Newcomers’ needs to earn a wage allowing sending remittances (UK).
- Language barriers which sometimes obstruct newcomers’ access to locals and services such as specialist medical treatment; unawareness of opportunities and services (UK).

Opportunities

- Exchange between migrants and locals easier to achieve in more remote and rural municipalities because ethnic communities less dominant and integration structures smaller and, thus, easier to manage. (AU-Vorarlberg)
- Migration to rural areas is a chance to revitalise them. Alleviate the weakening demography, provide a valuable work force to the troubled areas of the local labour market, bring their own networks with them which can be beneficial culturally, socially, and economically (Austria, Bulgaria, Finland, Germany, Italy, Norway, Spain, UK).

- Covid-19 as a catalyst for return mobility and return. Most returnees well educated and relatively young; positive impact on the attractiveness of the territory (BG-Haskovo).
- Potential of amenity migration to foster the understanding of the migration as a resource for local development (BG-Haskovo).
- Potential of a minority language: in the Swedish (official, yet less spoken language in Finland) speaking Ostrobothnia the good relations between different groups comparatively easier to achieve (FIN-Ostrobothnia)
- Local need of labour force in different economic sectors (IT-South Tyrol, IT-MC Turin)
- Local need for new inhabitants (IT-MC Turin)
- Welcoming attitudes towards migrants (IT-MC Turin, IT-South Tyrol)
- Lower cost of life in rural/mountain villages (IT-MC Turin)
- Civil society initiatives and social enterprises (IT-South Tyrol, IT-MC Turin)
- Already existing rural problems became more salient because of presence of TCNs – spark action (Germany)
- Volunteers discovered as a valuable complement to the administration (Germany)
- Identification of strategies for counteracting potential weaknesses, handling integration processes more as a collective societal responsibility, rather than as the main responsibility of the authorities and public services. (Norway)
- Greater rural-urban connection (Spain).
- Revitalization of civil society in rural areas, possibility of development of social enterprises (Spain).
- Participation a key enabler of social inclusion, volunteering fosters migrant access to the local society in terms of both cultural and social capital (UK, Sweden).
- Awareness of migrants' stories and experiences hold potential to change local perception, notably in the case of the refugees (UK).
- Skills built by local actors for the benefit of the Syrian refugees which can benefit other migrant groups and potentially also vulnerable locals are an asset to be preserved (UK).

Threats

- Tightened national migration regulation over the last years (Austria) which contradicts the interests at regional or municipal level (Norway)

- Residential and relational stratification (Spain), territorial concentration of migrants in particular neighbourhoods / formation and preference of ethnic communities with social control (AU-Carinthia; IT-South Tyrol, IT-MC Turin).
- Anti-migration mobilizations by far-right nationalist parties, strengthening the fears and anxiety of the local population and undermining the conditions for social inclusion, fuelling polarization, weakened everyday security of both locals and newcomers. (Bulgaria; Finland). Populism, provincialism, and rising xenophobia (IT-South Tyrol, IT-MC Turin).
- Lack of experience with TCNs feed prejudices, rumours, and myths about TCNs and foster polarization (Germany)
- Risk of isolation and segregation if integration unsuccessful, further risk of consequent negative impact (Finland; Germany), Separate coexistence between migrants and locals (IT-MC Turin, IT-South Tyrol).
- Low skills job offers (IT-South Tyrol, IT-MC Turin)
- Excessive bureaucracy for migrants (IT-South Tyrol, IT-MC Turin)
- Infantilization of migrants, instead of their empowerment (IT-South Tyrol, IT-MC Turin).
- Legal insecurity of TCNs (Germany)
- Lacking (psychological) well-being of TCNs (Germany, Finland)
- Lack of financial resources of TCNs hampers their participation (Germany, Finland, Sweden)
- Lack of interest among locals in interaction with TCNs (Germany)
- Lacking positions in administration and non-statutory welfare providers dealing with social integration of TCNs that are on an indefinite contract basis (Germany)
- The weaknesses of existing strategies are sustained or reinforced (Norway).
- Concentration of unqualified job (Spain).
- Development model centred on economic growth (Spain).
- National legislative limitation to participate in electoral processes among TCNs (Spain).
- Reproduction of social structures of origin that prevent the development of women belonging to endogamic groups, hinders socialization of the second generation (Spain).
- Approaching gender equality in integration processes is complicated (Sweden).
- Competition among the most vulnerable groups concerning social assistance and job opportunities carries the risks of further tensions, competition more intense during Covid-19 pandemic – makes social assistance to immigrants also more visible in a negative sense (Turkey).

While significant differences can be observed between the different MATILDE countries, regions and localities, the findings gathered seem to support the main hypotheses of the project, even if with their particular nuances. Rural and mountainous regions of Europe, the regions left behind, hold a great potential not only for the immigrants themselves or their respective new host societies, but – above all – for something new to be created together and shared with others in the very process of redefining it. It is therein that lies impact. Migration to rural areas provides a chance to revitalise them by alleviating the common challenges many of these regions are faced with: weakening demography and the lack of work force in the troubled areas of the local labour market together with the multiple side effects, such as diminishing services, weakening public transportation options, and the general waning on of social and cultural capital. Participation on behalf of the migrants seem to be a key enabler social inclusion, while greater awareness of migrants' stories and experiences among the host population is crucial in order to change the local perception, often reserved by default, on immigrants, particularly refugees.

The anxieties stemming from the dissolving of the invisible social glue and the self's resulting from re-bordering create a sense of ontological insecurity that, in turn, triggers antagonistic perceptions of difference and anti-immigrant attitudes (Laine 2020a, 232). The accentuation of the perceived difference between states, cultures, and people becomes a major risk, which increases within contexts of socioeconomic stress and instability – the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic being a pertinent case in point. Following (Ahmed 2017, 32), strangers are not those who we do not recognize, but those who we recognize as strangers; that is, defining “them” – and thus also “us” is first and the foremost a conscious process. The feeling of ontological insecurity has led to the defence of actions that have manifested themselves in antagonism towards others, fuelling misrepresentations of immigration (cf. Laine 2020a), alternative narratives to which needs to be provided to better understand the utterly complex migratory trajectories in their full complexity. Migration, particularly that of an irregular kind, to Europe has become a field where estimations often prevail over researched actualities, and hearsay and myths govern over concrete evidence (Laine 2020b, 93). The earlier reports compiled within this WP (D3.2 and D3.2.), which include detailed information collected by the MATILDE research partners, make valuable contributions to this end in assessing the concrete impact of migration in both quantitative and qualitative terms.

The research conducted suggest the social impact of immigration to be largely positive in the analysed MATILDE regions. A positive social impact of immigration is not, however, the same – not at least instinctively – as successful integration. A positive social impact of immigration is more than

just integration; it is about the well-functioning of a society. Integration remains as a pivotal concept – and above all, a purpose built administrative tool used to describe how immigrants find their way in a new country and become a part of it; that is, to measure both the socio-economic incorporation of immigrants in the host society, and to their socio-cultural adaptation to that society. While the various approaches of integration have the proven benefits, as an analytical concept intended as descriptive and progressive is often used in a rather normative manner.

Assuming the integration perspective can be illuminative but may also obscure. There is a need to question the very assumptions on which the concept rests (Cf. Schinkel 2018), rather than taking them a priori. Integration serves a purpose, but a magic bullet it is not. In any assessment of it, it is important to be specific about what the purpose is that is being worked towards with the help of integration. The assessments and the applicability of the terms varies greatly based on whether we understand integration as a mere administrative or bureaucratic ladder a migrant needs to climb in order to gain certain status and rights in her or his new host society or whether we are talking about a broader wellbeing and coherence on that society. Successful integration is dependent not only on the characteristics and abilities of the immigrant, but also on those of the receiving society. Social impact can also occur without integration.

The concept of integration used commonly to imply that immigrants integrate into a nation-state, and that the given state would have a somewhat coherent nation that would serve as sort of natural frame of reference towards which the migrants ought to aspire for. Using the various national models as a yardstick may well be worthwhile if integration is taken as a mere administrative process, yet if a more analytical angle is assumed one ought to question to what degree the said national models actually provide adequate descriptions of reality in the first place. As Meissner (2019) argues, in conducting migration research one must be cautious not to contribute to harmful Othering in replicating simplistic conceptions of society. To what extent, to take the argumentation further, an immigrant should seek to integrate into “society” (vis-à-vis, e.g. incorporation and inclusion into the social life, culture, economy) to begin with should be at least considered, particularly so when migrant impact is being assessed. The results gathered within MATILDE so far suggest that there might be valuable avenues to be considered in extending the analytical scope beyond the conventional forms of integration research and centre the conversation around inclusion, engagement and belongingness in envisioning an imagination out of the box (of a nation-state) and against the grain of the common integration logic without resorting to the take-for-granted categories in doing so.

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